

Funded by
the European Union

D5.1. Stakeholder and User Engagement Plan

Funded by
the European Union

General information

Project name	AgroServ Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
Deliverable	5.1. Stakeholder and User Engagement Plan
Work package	WP5 – Community building and users' engagement
Grant agreement n°	101058020
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01
Project duration	01.09.2022 - 31.08.2027 (60 months)
Project coordinator	Michel Boër michel.boer@anaee.eu
Dissemination level	Public
Main author	Soto-Embodas Iria, Caro Daniel, Chaves Francisco with the support of WP1, WP2, WP4, WP6, WP7 and WP8.
Date of approval	
Approved by	
Submission date	

Version history

Version n°	Date	Description
V1.0	01.06.2023	First draft version
V1.1.	22.06.2023	Version including WP8 suggestions
V1.2.	04.07.2023	Version including WP1 suggestions

Contents

Glossary	4
Executive summary	5
1. Objectives	6
2. Methodological approach	6
3. Challenges for stakeholders' engagement	7
4. Mapping of AgroServ stakeholders	8
4.1. Stakeholders' definition	8
4.2. Stakeholders' and user's categorization	10
4.2.1. Stakeholders' typology	10
4.2.2. Geographical representation	11
4.2.3. Fields of expertise of the community of users	12
4.2.5. Agroecology transition levels & principles	14
4.2.6. Value chain links	15
5. Engagement and communication in AgroServ project	15
5.1. Guidelines for involving the community of users	16
5.2. General principles for facilitating participatory processes	18
5.3. Participatory methods and tools	19
5.3.1. Participatory information collection and data sharing	20
5.3.2. Facilitating connection among the group	20
5.3.3. Ideas sharing and definition	20
5.3.4. Matchmaking	21
5.3.5. Needs assessment & understanding contexts	21
5.3.6. Strategic future scenarios	22
5.3.7. Online facilitating meetings & discussions	22
5.3.8. Where to get more info?	23
6. AgroServ stakeholders & users engagement activities	23
7. Evaluation of the engagement activities	34
8. List of forums for communication and engagement	34
10. Conclusions	39
Annexes	42

Glossary¹

Term	Description
Access manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure
Access provider	Manage of a specific installation or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure
AE	Agroecology
Agro-Serv	The present project
Installation	Facility or service for the implementation of a specific service, a synonym a facility specifically with respect to access to experimental services
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
SUEP	Stakeholders and users engagement plan
TNA	Trans-National Access. Allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities and services.
VA	Virtual Access. Allowing third-party researchers to access an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services.
WP(s)	Work Package(s). A set of related activities within a project.

¹ <https://agroserv.eu/node/76>

Executive summary

The Stakeholders and Users Engagement Plan (SUEP) aims at developing a master plan to create and engage a community of users interested in using the AgroServ services. This deliverable is a living document that will be used to guide engagement actions within the AgroServ consortium. It will provide the appropriate co-design methodologies and tools to ensure that the proposed AgroServ service pipeline are customized and adapted to the community of users' needs. In close collaboration with the communication package, the SUEP will also serve to coordinate the work on specific stakeholders and outreach activities and events.

This document is structured in 9 sections:

- **Section 1 & 2**– Provides a short introduction of the deliverable and outlines how the document frames into AgroServ project and Agroecological transition
- **Section 3** - Presents the main objectives and the methodological approach used to draft the SUEP.
- **Section 4** - Assesses the complexity and challenges associated with drafting an engagement plan for the AgroServ project.
- **Section 5** – Provides guidelines for involving the community of users and general principles to consider when facilitating participatory processes. A selection of participatory tools and methods for the engagement of stakeholders in the different activities of the project is also presented (detailed guidelines are to be found in the Annex section of this document).
- **Section 6** - Plans the different project activities in which involvement with stakeholders is foreseen.
- **Section 7** - Provides insight on how to monitor and report the different engagement processes.
- **Section 8**- Presents a list of forums and events for communication and engagement purposes.
- **Section 9**- Provides final conclusions for future stakeholders' engagement actions.

1. Objectives

The main objectives of this Stakeholders and users' engagement plan (SUEP) are five-fold:

1. Plan the co-creation, participatory and engagement activities that will take place under the different Work Packages (WPs) of the AgroServ Work project. The activities for each group of users will be listed while paying attention to their group characteristics
2. Provide a participatory and co-creation framework for assessing the success of the engagement tools and methods used, which could improve the successful engagement of stakeholders in the different project activities
3. Develop a database of potential AgroServ services users for communication, outreach and engagement purposes and assess their characteristics (e.g. domain of expertise, geographical distribution)
4. Provide a list of events relevant to AgroServ. Those events are important to ensure that the different RIs and partners communicate and engage with stakeholders.
5. Ensure efficient coordination in the involvement of the community of users when receiving the needed support to apply and access to TNA services.

2. Methodological approach

The SUEP is intended to be a living document that will be used to guide engagement actions conducted by the AgroServ consortium.

Firstly, we started with identifying RI stakeholders and users that we could potentially engage with during the project duration. We conducted an online survey² to request information to identify the different stakeholders (M1-M3). We differentiated the stakeholders that could potentially belong to the "community of users" (as beneficiaries of the provision of services) from the other type of stakeholders with whom we could engage for other purposes in the project. The different characteristics of the identified stakeholders have been mapped and characterised according to a set of criteria (section 4) to have a general overview of their potential thematic interests and representativeness. These lists will be reviewed and updated by partners during AgroServ project lifespan.

Secondly, we have provided tips to ensure the successful involvement of the community of users in the project and to facilitate the participatory process. We have also identified participatory, co-design, animation and engagement methods that could be used within the framework of this project not only by RIs and access managers, but also by the consortium to ensure effective mobilisation of LLs members (WP6) and the engagement of other actors.

Third, in collaboration with the different WPs, we have identified the tasks that might need to involve collaborative communication and outreach activities in addition to stakeholder engagement to plan,

² [Stakeholders mapping survey](#)

Funded by
the European Union

inform and share knowledge around co-building proposals. Thus, enhancing coordination and preventing repetitive and redundant communication to ensure fruitful and meaningful involvement of stakeholders. We also propose activities for evaluating the engagement activities and provide a template to be used by partners when performing engagement activities.

Lastly, we provide a list of events (to communicate and engage with the agroecology community).

3. Challenges for stakeholders' engagement

3.1. The AgroServ project

AgroServ supports the development of a large community in line with the goals of research towards agroecological transitions. The project aims to facilitate a systematic and holistic approach to understand the threats and challenges agriculture is facing. It focuses on implementing a resilient and sustainable agri-food system, with a transdisciplinary offer of services from research infrastructures, while integrating the actors of the agriculture system in the research process.

The AgroServ project utilises a multi-actor approach which considers that various groups of stakeholders active in the Agroecological transition are central in defining innovative, customised, and efficient services offered by the RIs. These will include mainly researchers, but also farmers, industries, cooperatives, SMEs, rural communities, public health authorities and policymakers that will be involved in activities to improve, customise, and integrate the services the infrastructures provide.

AgroServ needs to generate a Community of Users, providing appropriate methodologies and ensuring that the proposed AgroServ services pipeline are co-designed and co-developed to fit the needs of its community to support the research activities that will be developed in the partnership through the provision of scientific data, computing, communication systems and dedicated research sites.

3.2. The AgroServ Consortium

AgroServ is a **large consortium of 12 RIs** in which a high number of **partners (73)** work together to provide operational excellence by delivering and developing high-quality, interoperable, integrated and customized services to foster transition towards agroecology and sustainable agriculture systems.

The **large number and variety of institutions working together** entails a series of challenges and complexities that need to be well understood for drafting this SUEP plan. Effective collaborative approaches involving partnerships with stakeholders from different disciplines and sectors is needed to foster knowledge exchange and integration across disciplines and sectors (Borger et al., 2017).

Proposals developed under AgroServ are **expected to link stakeholders from different disciplines and sectors**. Thus, research sector should try to link with actors from other sectors such as farmers, industry, cooperatives, SMEs, rural communities, and policymakers. This entails the co-production of knowledge that transcends disciplinary and sectoral boundaries and establishes a common language

and research practices to solve common issues. This approach is crucial for understanding and addressing complex, real-world, context-specific, needs-driven and multifaceted problems for which traditional and uni-disciplinary approaches are inadequate (Grigorovich et al., 2019). The collaborative team approach requires researchers to work with stakeholders as partners from the beginning to identify a real-world problem, understand the multi-layered issues that surround it, co-develop project objectives, and co-design and implement the project ideas. The complexity of engaging interdisciplinarity in building proposals to conduct research with real applications requires **active mobilization** of multidisciplinary and multi-actor users by RI access managers.

An additional complexity is the importance of AgroServ in generating cutting-edge results and user input for a **holistic transition towards agroecology** and resilient and sustainable agriculture. There is a need to move from building TNA proposals that generate research-based solutions aimed at using conventional agricultural and land-use approaches to build proposals that support the integrated conversion towards agroecological systems and resilience and sustainable agriculture. Therefore, clear communication, active involvement of both potential users and diverse RI access managers in the proposal preparation phase, and setting clear guidelines and eligibility criteria aligned with agroecology and sustainable agriculture principles need to be implemented.

Lastly, the AgroServ project has a mayor challenge in **demonstrating to the entire EU agricultural community the important role that Research Infrastructures have on mainstreaming the agroecological transition** and fostering innovation. The RIs role lie in reducing the fragmentation of research and innovation ecosystems, avoiding duplication of effort and upscaling results by joining forces internationally to construct and run large, complex and open-science experiments, thus, responding to global challenges and fostering the combination of skills, data and efforts of the world's best scientists. Additionally, RIs should make the industry, policy makers and other stakeholders more aware of opportunities offered to improve products through the co-development of advanced technologies.

4. Mapping of AgroServ stakeholders

4.1. Stakeholders' definition

The AgroServ project aims at involving different types of stakeholders from different sectors and disciplines. We identified different targeted groups of stakeholders' (figure 1):

- **Scientific community** – All research actors involved in Agricultural Sciences, Natural Sciences, Biological Sciences, Ecology, Forestry, Fisheries, Agronomy, Social Sciences, Plant Protection and Ecosystems, etc. We have identified two sub-groups:
 - Research institutions (e.g. universities, research centres)
 - European initiatives & research projects (e.g. Eco-Ready)
- **Agriculture community** – where 2 major groups are differentiated:
 - Agrifood businesses – industries dealing with agricultural products and services required in farming. They can be both large or small and medium enterprises (SME).

- Agrifood cooperatives, associations and farmers–this group includes NGOs, producers and food industry organisations (e.g. COPA COGECA, ELO, IFOAM Organic EU)
- **Networks** – multidisciplinary and/or multi-actor initiatives and groups of interconnected actors from different backgrounds (e.g. Living labs, ENoLL, Cities for Agroecology). They are key actors in AgroServ due to the transdisciplinary and multi- actor nature of the project and their intended services. LLs are specific target stakeholders as they have been identified as key players for boosting AE transition (EU, 2021).
- **Policy makers, public administrations and funding bodies** at EU Level (e.g. DGAGRI, DGENVI), national, regional and local level.
- **The press and the general public** – The involvement in the project will be targeted by the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (WP8).

Those different stakeholders’ types are classified by the type of engagement objective in the AgroServ project in two broad categories: The **community of users and the AE community in general**. The community of users are those individuals that will directly use the different AgroServ services provision through the AgroServ call for applications. The AE community in general are those individuals, parties or institutions active in AE transition and that have an interest or stake in AgroServ and the services provided by the RIs and its installations. This group will potentially benefit from the results of the project and we will liaise with them to ensure long-term sustainability of AgroServ’s results by generating synergies through knowledge-sharing, consultation, partnership and dissemination of AgroServ activities. This AE community group of stakeholders will be addressed through the Initial report on clustering and liaising with other initiatives (Deliverable 5.3) as part of Task 5.2 Clustering and Liaising with other relevant initiatives and projects.

Figure 1. Stakeholders group definition in AgroServ project

4.2. Stakeholders' and user's categorization

To identify stakeholders with whom we could initially engage in the AgroServ project, a survey¹ was conducted among the different RIs participating in the consortium. The survey contains 20 questions structured in 5 sections: 1. RI information, 2. Stakeholders and user contact details, 3. Stakeholder typology, 4. Areas of expertise, 5. Engagement characterisation.

A total of 180 different stakeholders were identified by the different RI partners (figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of the stakeholders by RI. Dark blue represents the RI while light blue represents the partners associated with that RI.

4.2.1. Stakeholders' typology

Among the full list of identified stakeholders (Annex 1), around half of them (48%) belong to the scientific community including RIs, universities or research centres (figure 3). A quarter (25%) of the identified stakeholders belong to agricultural associations and organizations active in the full agriculture production value chain. Large and SME agribusinesses represent 14% of the identified stakeholders. Networks, although highly relevant for transdisciplinary and multi-actor TNA applicants only represent 6% (the same share as public sector).

When looking only at the potential community of users (figure 3, lower graph), the majority of identified stakeholders belong to the research community (54%) followed by “Agrifood associations & organizations” (20%), large agribusinesses (8%) and SME agribusinesses (6%), networks (6%) and public sector (6%). Only 11% of total stakeholders were identified as non-potential users of AgroServ services but as stakeholders to liaise with. They mainly belong to agriculture associations and cooperatives (65%) followed by large agribusiness (10%).

While the most relevant type of engagement objective for stakeholders in AgroServ was through the TNA application (89%), they were also identified for dissemination (47%), training (27%), consultation (23%) and partnering (23%) purposes (figure 2, right chart).

Figure 3. Stakeholders' typology. The left chart represents the type of organization where the stakeholder belongs while the right graph represents the main engagement typologies as identified by AgroServ partners

4.2.2. Geographical representation

The geographical scope of the community of users identified by AgroServ partners are mainly at the national, European and international level with similar shares (30%, 29% and 25% respectively). Only 11% of them performed their activities locally (figure 4, left upper side).

The European regional representation of the stakeholders and users mapped is well covered with higher number of stakeholders coming from South and Central Eastern EU (figure 4, lower side). Only 5 member states (i.e. Croatia, Poland, Bulgaria, Slovakia and Croatia) are not represented.

The institution headquarters where the community of users belong are mainly based in Italy (37 of them) and Spain (33) followed by UK (18), Rumania (11), Belgium (9), Check Republic (8), Germany and Finland (7 respectively). There is only one institution identified in Denmark, Estonia, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Luxemburg, Slovenia and Switzerland (figure 4, right upper side).

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of the community of AgroServ services users

4.2.3. Fields of expertise of the community of users

The fields of expertise of the community of users were assessed in two ways. First, according to the Frascati (2015) classification and secondly according to the specific classification of the AgroServ scientific domains developed for the catalogue of services established in WP2.

The field of expertise of the majority of the community of users identified belong to Agriculture & veterinary sciences (69%) and Natural Sciences (36%) (figure 5). Thus, being aligned with the widely majority of RI services offered under AgroServ project. Humanity and arts together with Medical and Health Studies (broad classification) is only relevant for 5% of the community of users. The 4 most relevant second level classifications correspond to Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries, Biological Sciences, Animal and Dairy Sciences, Earth and related Environmental Sciences. Veterinary Sciences, Agricultural Biotechnology and other Agricultural Sciences rank after those four first ones.

The scientific domain of most identified potential users is Environmental Science & Agroecosystem (30%) followed by Agronomy, Farm Management and Aquaculture, Fisheries and Marine Sciences (figure 6). The less identified scientific domain is Rangeland Management. Around a fifth (19%) of users belong to the Organic Agriculture field of expertise.

Figure 5. Share of Fields of expertise (broad and second level classification) of the potential community of users (Frascati, 2015).

Figure 6. Share of specific scientific domains mentioned by the community of users (classification used for the catalogue of services established in WP2)

4.2.5. Agroecology transition levels & principles

Agroecology is a way of redesigning food systems, from the farm to the table, with a goal of achieving ecological, economic, and social sustainability. Gliessman (2016) proposes a framework for classifying food system changes in five levels. The levels describe the steps farmers can actually take on their farms for converting from industrial or conventional agroecosystems. While level 1 relates to increasing the efficiency of industrial and conventional practices in order to reduce the use and consumption of costly, scarce, or environmentally damaging inputs, level 2 goes one step further, aiming to replace external input-intensive and environmentally degrading products and practices with those that are more renewable, based on natural and environmentally sound products. Level 3 generates fundamental changes by focusing on preventing problems before they occur, rather than trying to control them after they happen. Level four implies a food transformation within a cultural and economic context, and this transformation must promote the transition to more sustainable practices (e.g. consumption from locally grown and processed products). Level 5 involves a change in food systems paradigm going beyond the food system to the nature of human culture, civilization, progress, and development.

Agroecology transition levels (Gliessman, 2016)

Level 1: Increase efficiency of input use and reduce the use of environmental damaging inputs

Level 2: Substitute conventional inputs & practices with AE alternatives

Level 3: Redesign agroecosystems

Level 4: Reconnect consumers & producers (alternative food networks)

Level 5: Build a global food system

10 Agroecology principles (HLPE, 2019)

Figure 7. Share of potential users of AgroServ services under the different agroecological transition levels as defined by Gliessman (2016) (left chart). Share of the 3 most relevant agroecology principles identified by the community of users (right chart).

The activities of the majority of the community of potential users identified fall under the lowest AE transition level (73%), especially level 1 and 3 (figure 7). This might indicate that the potential users of AgroServ generated services have the niche to support agroecological transformation from the foundations. Therefore, the most important principles for the potential community of users are mainly (by order of importance) efficiency, diversity, resilience, synergies and recycling indicating alignment with the first 3 AE transition levels.

4.2.6. Value chain links

The potential users of the AgroServ services identified by partners are mainly active in the agriculture and food production domain (73%). However, a share of 41% users is also active in food and agriculture processing, food distribution (31%) and marketing (31%) (figure 8). The link in which users appear to be less active is the consumption phase.

Figure 8. Share of potential users of AgroServ services active in the different links of the agricultural food value chain

5. Engagement and communication in AgroServ

Communications and engagement are two functions or two different sets of actions and strategies necessary to the success of any project. They both mean different things, but they overlap and are complementary:

- To communicate= to convey knowledge or information
- To disseminate= to spread knowledge or information
- To exploit= to make productive use of knowledge or information
- To engage with= to become involved with

If communication is about crafting tailored key messages, curating information and news, and sharing them via the relevant communication channels with the objective to inform, spread knowledge, raise awareness and interest, engagement is active, bilateral and dialogue based, in the case of AgroServ, on a two-way interaction with stakeholders that could happen even on the stakeholders' channels to ensure better outcomes and better alignment with the project's objectives.

Therefore, communication is about keeping stakeholders updated and informed, while engagement involves acquiring hands-on knowledge on the needs and characteristics of each group of stakeholders, the focus in this sense being on their feedback and the meaningful conversation that will ensue once the communication is engaged.

Engagement will help the project along with its stakeholders share insights, spark innovative and creative ideas related to the subjects tackled through a problem-solving lens and help the project achieve more impact and widen its network of users.

Engagement follows the cycle of the project and is based on openness, collaboration, and dialogue. The engagement strategy should be defined according to what the project needs during each phase. Engagement cannot happen without communication and a communication campaign, even if successful, does not mean that the stakeholders will remain engaged, hence the need for follow-ups and meaningful and sustained interactions over time.

In AgroServ **access managers** and **access providers** are essential for stakeholders' engagement as promoters of the services provided by the TNA calls for tenders. They should encourage dialogue and co-creation among their final users of their services and installations.

5.1. Guidelines for involving the community of users

This section provides a selection of key elements to ensure efficient and successful involvement of stakeholder in the provision of AgroServ services and might prevent engagement barriers.

- **Effective communication.** communication aims at raising awareness among stakeholders. It has long been recognised as the most relevant factor for projects success (Schmitz et al, 2018). There are different common factors that involve users with media: strong cognitive and emotional focus on media content; attraction, curiosity, and interest toward the medium or interface; and voluntary participation influenced by media content (Oh & Sundar, 2016). Thus, it is essential to consolidate appropriate communication channels and produce content within the AgroServ project with the potential to raise awareness, capture the attention of the targeted audience and trigger user engagement. Special attention should be given to engagement in navigation tools on e.g., catalogue of services and general websites. They are the entrance gate to potential users of the consortium, its service pipeline, project activities and results. They are visited by different types of target audience and its navigation and content should be adapted not only to people that have a clear interest in the project but also to people not aware of it. Communication content should serve to achieve the set of goals for the targeted users, by being creative and appealing (e.g. visual material instead of text content) and not too intense to provide users value and increase involvement. A common and homogeneous language, familiar to users (with an appropriate level of technicality) should be mainstream among the different RIs and users for appropriate onboarding, information sharing and collaboration in the context of the AgroServ project.
- **Co-creation process.** Co-creation has recently become an extremely widespread and popularised term. It's not only used on consumer-centred discourse but also on multi-stakeholders' platforms such as public-private partnerships and living labs involving innovation and research. Co-creation in the private sectors is described as the process of value creation through the active collaboration of the consumers by allowing them to co-develop the product and service experience to fit their needs (Kambil et al. 1999). However, in the context of the AgroServ project co-creation should be aligned with the living labs co-creation concept which refers to a form of open innovation, where the creation of new value takes place in cooperation between the experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, research, public institutions,

and civil society, in which the inputs of the user play a central role (Hagy et al. 2016, Mambrini-Doudet et al. 2021). Therefore, the involvement of multiple stakeholders creates a multi-contextual scene in which the actors engage and interact with other stakeholders during every step of the co-creation process from problem definition to piloting (Ballon et al. 2005, Kreiling and Paunov 2021). This can mobilize and bring together complementary and transversal agroecological expertise which increases the speed and uptake of innovations while also increasing awareness and relevance of agroecological transition and, at the same time, addressing socio-economic challenges via the involvement of civil society. According to Puerari et al. (2018) five elements should be considered in co-creation processes: 1) purpose of co-creation (i.e. working towards a common goal or an outcome, or focusing on learning itself), 2) formal cocreation (when intermediaries define the procedures and steps) or informal (when emerges out of necessity), 3) ownership (predominant role comes from users), 4) motivation (the benefits and expectations of the cocreation process need to be well articulated), 5) spaces for co-creation (Co-creation occurs in a place-based (often local) socio-spatial context adapted to specific conditions).

- **Personalised approach to users.** Developing personalized onboarding process with tactics to create customised users experience have been proved to be effective in users' engagement (Kujala, 2003). Practices such as early assessment of users' needs, prototyping and iterative usability of services evaluation are key and cost-effective as they can reduce the time and costs of development efforts through early identification (and resolution) of usability problems. Adjusting the RI access provision to what the users expected will provide them with a positive experience and an added-value. Additionally current satisfied users, for which a quality access has been provided, can act as influencer to boost and encourage the adoption and involvement in the project of new ones. Social media sharing through testimonials, recommendations and successful result are essential to enlarge the community of users. Rewarding and recognition approaches to current users can also support the expansion of the community of users.
- **Reflective monitoring and evaluation approach.** Effective and sustainable engagement of stakeholders implies the evaluation of the process pathway not only at the end of the process but when the work is still on-going (Alvarez et al., 2010). Reflective and adaptative approaches align daily activities with long-term ambitions and adapts to generate aimed impact of a project activities. The method enables users to gain insight into the progress and direction of their project in real time. Reflexive Monitoring helps to evaluate day-to-day activities and to respond to them while considering the bigger picture. This is especially helpful when addressing complex challenges. Active listening and feedback gathering from users, starting from the onboarding process to the finalisation of the service provision is essential to improve the **learning process** of users, researchers and other stakeholders. Day-to-day questioning and challenging our ideas, assumptions and thinking of alternatives and adaptative measures helps to improve the quality of the services provided.
- **Community building activities.** Building interactions and connections among groups helps to create a sense of belonging and connection among members to boost collaboration. Therefore, linking potential users among them and with access managers by means of webinars, workshops, working sessions and training is essential to promote exchanges of visions, ideas, potential needs and technical solutions between the various disciplinary communities involved, resulting in common proposals and synergies creations.

5.2. General principles for facilitating participatory processes

There are certain principles and guidelines that need to be considered for the implementation of project activities that seek to involve actors in a participatory and meaningful way. Here we suggest the following tips to enhance success in the facilitation of co-creative approaches during the involvement of users in project activities:

- **Facilitators key roles and responsibilities.** Facilitation is an art, science or skill. Good facilitators should play 3 major roles for collaborative innovation (Brouwer et al., 2019). Act as **convener** that bring together relevant members and stimulates interaction by motivating them to participate, giving direction to reach the goals and expectations. Act as **moderator**, getting actors to collaborate in their differences and supporting mutual learning by arranging effective and quality meetings, ensuring smooth communication and common understanding. Act as **catalyser** by stimulating stakeholders to think outside the box, enhance creativity in the discussion and preventing tunnel vision by encouraging actors to change their perspective. Facilitation doesn't have to be all conducted by a single individual: a group of people with a combination of these competencies can also make a successful team (especially if from different cultural and professional background).

Table 1 – Key competences of successful facilitation processes

Key facilitating competencies

- *Active listening*
 - *Forward thinking and ability to make synthesis*
 - *Identifying key challenges and opportunities*
 - *Bridging between different actors from various backgrounds and thus different ways of thinking*
 - *Understanding co-design methods*
 - *Facilitating user-drive process*
 - *Making a shared goal*
 - *Methodological skills*
 - *In-depth knowledge about processes*
-
- **Process matters - plan the session.** Although participatory sessions may seem straightforward process they need to be designed. Thus, it is essential to plan beforehand the participatory working session. We need to consciously think about the activities, methodologies and tools that are needed to achieve the desired outcomes. There is a need to set an agenda defining the purpose, outcomes as well as the means (methods and materials) that are needed to achieve a given goal. Select a team to animate the session, define their roles and assign responsibilities for the different sessions of the event. As a recommendation “Be strong on your mission but flexible on the details of how you get there” (Brouwer et al., 2019).

- **Choosing appropriate methods and tools.** Methods and tools are what we used to transform our theoretical understanding into practice. Facilitation approaches are full of creative ideas, and new ideas are being developed all the time. Next section 6.4. provides a range of methods and tools that we believe are of interest for the different specific activities of this project.
- **Choose the right target group participants and size.**
- **Breath neutrality.** Facilitators should be transparent to the group and should help the group to move through the discussion trying to bring stakeholders together and integrating their different perspectives without positioning themselves.
- **Animate discussion.** Asking open questions to participants helps to move the conversations and ensures that people are being heard not only listened to.
- **Prevent non-participation.** It is important to notice who is and is not talking to include everyone in the discussion, addressing power dynamics, creating belonging and increasing meaningful participation.
- **Devolution.** It is important to always summarize the action points and outcome of the participatory working sessions and explain the next steps and how the information and knowledge obtained will be used. Once the working session has been analysed, the results obtained should be shared back with participants, thus ensuring transparency and inclusion.

5.3. Participatory methods and tools

In this section we present a selection (from the hundreds available) of methods and tools that we find especially useful to support the engagement process of stakeholders through participatory groups, stakeholders' community, consortium and proposal building dynamization. These selected approaches have been identified as relevant for the different involvement actions foreseen in the implementation of AgroServ activities (section 6). They can be used by both RI services providers, RI access managers as well as partners of the AgroServ consortium. Here we provide a list organised by aim:

- Participatory data collection and sharing
- Facilitating connection among the group
- Ideas sharing and definition
- Matchmaking
- Need assessment
- Strategic future scenarios

5.3.1. Participatory information collection and data sharing

The AgroServ project needs to gather information on the domains of expertise of its community of users, the quality of the service provision, the TNA application process, potential ethical issues of the services provided, among others. In this section we provide different tools to gather this information which are further detailed in the Annex 2.

Table 2 – Selection of tools for data collection and data sharing

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Surveys	To gather structured information and feedback from a target group.	Annex 2 , page 51
Interviews	To gather detailed insights, experiences, and feedback from a target group.	Annex 2 , page 52
Focus groups & working sessions	To gain insight into the experiences and perspectives of various stakeholders.	Annex 2 , page 53
Testimonials	To get positive feedback from users and build trust and credibility.	Annex 2 , page 53

5.3.2. Facilitating connections among the group

The word “facilitate” originated from the Latin word “*facilis*” which means “easy”. Thus, the role of the facilitator is to make conversations, discussions, and decisions easy for the group. Different tools and formats can be used for facilitation. In this section we propose two tools to support the facilitation process. More information on the tools can be found at the Annex 2.

Table 3 – Selection of tools for facilitating connection among the group

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Icebreakers activities	To break down initial barriers, create a sense of belonging, and set a conducive tone for further discussions and collaboration.	Annex 2 , page 53
Energizers	To re-energise participants, increase focus, and promote active engagement during meetings, workshops, or other gatherings.	Annex 2 , page 54

5.3.3. Ideas sharing and definition of ideas

A first challenge that may be encountered in the development of the AgroServ project is the identification of needs or challenges that need to be addressed. Idea definition with the partners is key for robust project preparation. Creativity is appreciated at these early stages of collective idea identification. The following tools are proposed for ideas sharing and definition. Further details on those tools are available in the Annex 2.

Table 4 – Selection of tools for ideas sharing and definition

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Brainstorming	To facilitate the exploration of a subject and to generate ideas.	Annex 2 , page 55
Word coffee	To informally collect ideas on a topic of mutual interest by fostering open dialogue, active listening, and the exploration of different perspectives.	Annex 2 , page 56
Speedboat	To explore ideas and research agreement on work programming by identifying constraints and opportunities.	Annex 2 , page 57

5.3.4. Matchmaking

In AgroServ matchmaking is needed not only among the different RIs access managers but also with and among the community of users. Here we present some tools for supporting this matchmaking process, more details on these tools are explained in the Annex 2.

Table 5 – Tool for matchmaking

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Elevator pitch	To convey key information/ ideas within a short timeframe, typically lasting as long as an elevator ride in a concise and compelling presentation.	Annex 2 , page 57

5.3.5. Needs assessment & understanding contexts

The assessment of needs and contexts of the different users and stakeholders is key for AgroServ. It will help bridge the gap between what the consortium can offer and what the potential users might need. Here we propose some tools that might help to understand the underlying problems faced in an Agroecological transition context. . Detailed information on those tools can be found in Annex 2.

Table 6 – Selection of tools for assessing needs and understanding contexts

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Problem tree	Structurally identify and analyse the causes and effects of a specific problem or issue.	Annex 2 , page 58
Canvas Value Proposition	Understand users' needs & how the product/service generated can create value for your user and meet users' expectation.	Annex 2 , page 59
Six Thinking Hats	Assess a decision, problem or need from different perspectives to foster structured and collaborative thinking.	Annex 2 , page 59
Participatory SWOT analysis	Identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the consortium's project or results.	Annex 2 , page 60
Delphi	Gather expert opinions and achieve consensus on project outcomes or future actions.	Annex 2 , page 60

5.3.6. Strategic future scenarios

In the AgroServ project, there is a need to enhance collaboration and ownership on proposal development among a variety of disciplines, actors and scale. Tools that support setting a common future vision with clear goals, bridging divergent opinions into a common vision and mutual understanding is key for successful service provision. A set of tools aiming at boosting this strategic collaboration are mentioned below (table 7) and described in Annex 2.

Table 7 – Selection of tools for future scenarios planning

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Visioning - Vision Development	Engage stakeholders in creating a shared vision for the consortium's future, guiding its strategic direction and actions.	Annex 2 , page 61
Five Bold Steps	Facilitate a systematic approach for developing and implementing transformative actions and strategies.	Annex 2 , page 62
Three Types of Knowledge Tool	Adapt project considerations to align with the specific knowledge requirements of stakeholders by integrating three distinct knowledge perspectives.	Annex 2 , page 62
Toolbox Dialogue Approach	Uncover implicit assumptions and shared understandings among stakeholders from different disciplines for enhanced collaboration.	Annex 2 , page 63
Research Marketplace	Foster spontaneous interactions and idea collection within diverse research teams and with societal actors.	Annex 2 , page 64

5.3.7. Online facilitating meetings & discussions

The rise in the number of events, meeting and working sessions taking place virtually or in a hybrid format makes the use of online platforms and tools essential for easing interaction, exchange and setting a common understanding. These tools allow information visualization facilitating real-time collaboration among the different working sessions participants. The following tools are the most commonly used. A comparison of their functionalities and added value can be found in Annex 2.

Table 8 – Selection of data dashboards tools for online meeting facilitation

Tool	Aim	Detailed information
Miro	Visualise online data to explore, analyse or evaluate information	Annex 2 , page 65
Mural	Visualise online data to explore, analyse or evaluate information	Annex 2 , page 65
Jamboard	Visualise online data to explore, analyse or evaluate information	Annex 2 , page 65

5.3.8. Where to get more information?

Brouwer, H., Woodhill, J., Hemmati, M., Verhoosel, K., & van Vugt, S. (2015). The MSP guide. How to design and facilitate multi-stakeholder partnerships. Centre for Development Innovation, Wageningen UR, Wageningen. ISBN 978-1-85339-965-7

UNaLab Project - Tools for Co-creation <https://unalab.enoll.org/>

6. AgroServ stakeholders & users engagement activities

Agroecology is characterised by its transdisciplinary, participatory, and action-oriented nature, encompassing the whole food system from the soil to the organisation of human societies (Wezel et al., 2018). To promote a successful transition to agroecological farming systems, the AgroServ project should promote the integration of stakeholders' effort throughout the project and its different activities.

In this section we outline the different project activities involving the participation of the different AgroServ stakeholders and specifically the community of users. We therefore drafted, in collaboration with RIs partners, an implementation plan of the activities organized by the different WP task as described in Figure 9.

The criteria used for the description of activities were the following:

- **Engagement action aim and scope.** We define and explain the reasons why participation is necessary, with a focus on the objective for involving stakeholders.
- **Engagement methods and tools.** We propose a methodological approach with details further developed in section 6 and annex 2.
- **Timescale of engagement.** We identify the approximate timing when the different actions will take place in the project life period.
- **Previous anticipatory actions.** We identify required steps that need to take place before the involvement activities. They might be adapted during the activity implementation.
- **Target group.** We indicate the specific stakeholders targeted for each activity.
- **Foreseen number of participants.** We provide an estimation of the number of members involved in each action.

Figure 9. Description of the objectives of the different AgroServ work packages

Table 9. Description of the AgroServ project actions that will require the involvement of project stakeholders.

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Target group	N° of participants	Format of involvement
Task 1.3. Implementation and management of the TNA process					
Support the community of users to prepare TNA proposals: <i>consortium preparation- Preproposals</i>	Awareness raising (by means of communication material), Working sessions - Matchmaking, (Elevator pitch), Brainstorming, database of key contacts	1. Attract potential users to AgroServ by providing project information on the website and the AgroServ service portal 2. Identify the users registered in the platform 3. Match by topics of interest 4. Plan the working sessions	CoU	several hundred over 5 years	Both in-person ² and online
Support to the community of users to prepare TNA proposals: <i>Expression of interest-Preproposals</i>	Working sessions - Brainstorming, problems/needs tree, participatory SWOT analysis	1. Information on procedures is available on the website and the AgroServ service portal 2. Access manager of the RI participating in each proposal get in touch with potential applicants	CoU ¹	50-300 preproposals per call	Mainly online, potential in-person ²
Support to the community of users to prepare TNA proposals: <i>Finding the targeted required services</i>	Working sessions – Participatory SWOT analysis, value proposition CANVAS, Six thinking hats	1. Information on procedures is available on the website and the AgroServ service portal 2. Access manager of the RI participating and facility (service) managers in each proposal engage with potential applicants			
Support to the community of users to prepare TNA proposals: <i>Facilitating, stimulating inter-disciplinarity</i>	Working sessions - information contacts database, Elevator pitch to exchange experiences meetings, Six thinking hats	1. Information on procedures is available on the website and the AgroServ service portal 2. Access manager of the RI participating and facility (service) managers in each proposal engage with potential applicants			
Support to the community of users to prepare TNA proposals: <i>Full proposal preparation</i>	Working sessions (logical framework analysis, Value Proposition Canvas)	Access manager of the RI participating and facility (service) managers in each proposal engage potential applicants			
Assess the evolutions and needs of support during the implementation of the service provision	Follow- up/monitoring questionnaire developed by each specific RI following their own procedure and generally when services longer than 6 months	Identify the most relevant elements to be assessed (access managers with the central access coordinator)			
¹ Community of Users, animated by the panel of access managers and central access coordinator; ² in project conferences (WP.8)					

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Target group	# of participants	Format of involvement
Task 1.3. Implementation and management of the TNA process					
Evaluate the AgroServ service application process	Evaluation questionnaire with improvement recommendations, Testimonials	Identify the most relevant elements to be assessed (access managers with the central access coordinator)	CoU ¹	1-3 testimonials per call	Online & potentially in-person ²
Share feedback with applicants on how to improve the application for a potential resubmission	Written evaluation report with recommendations for improvement matching all categories of applicants (both rejected and accepted)	1. Selection of the Proposal Review Committee members to assess the proposal 2. Evaluation template development 3. Database with applicants and proposal scores	CoU (both rejected & accepted)	10-20 proposals	Online
Task 2.2. Developing AgroServ transdisciplinary approach supporting the Access Framework					
Identify the thematic and scientific priorities to align the AgroServ services customisation approach with the needs and challenges of the transition towards AE and sustainable agriculture	Working sessions (prioritization survey/tools, need assessment)	1. Pre-identification of potential topics to assess the needs and challenges of the sustainable transition towards agroecology 2. Identification of relevant stakeholders for the different topics (Annex 1) 3. Send an invitation to participate	RI + ESB ³ + other key external actors	15 internal + 15 externals (foreseen)	Online & Potentially in-person (during the conferences)
Task 2.3. Service pipelines clustering (M12-M58)					
Discuss, obtain inputs and feedback to test, refine, and validate the service pipeline integration, the information requirements and needs for the development of the RIs catalogue of services	Feedback gathering loops through surveys, interviews and focus groups discussions	Assessment of ISIA application to check the services provided by each RI and users demand	CoU - applicants to the services ¹	All users (survey), 12-20 persons (working sessions)	Online
Profiling potential users to monitor the evolution of the CoU interested in AgroServ services (e.g., actor type, field of expertise)	Survey (pop- up window that will appear upon access to the online catalogue)	1. Identification of the key most relevant questions needed 2. Online slash questioners	CoU	several hundred over 5 years	Online
Gather feedback to evaluate services provision integration and learn how to improve the integration of services provision	Working sessions – needs assessment	1. Identify the elements to be evaluated 2. Identify methodology 3. Identify the most requested service combination	RI ⁴ & CoU potentially	All service users	Online
¹ Community of Users, animated by the panel of access managers and central access coordinator ² in project conferences WP.8 ³ external scientific board ⁴ RI and facility service providers and access managers					

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Participants (target group)	number of participants	Format of involvement
Task 4.1. Access quality management & TNA projects monitoring					
Collect and exchange feedback of TNA users and facility managers regarding the quality of service provision	Short quality feedback survey (categorical questions)	1. identify quality indicators (in collaboration with WP1, WP2) 2. Define the elements to assess / question(s) to add	CoU ⁴	50-300 preproposals per call	Online
Collect and exchange on ethical issues during TNA proposal preparation (for self-evaluation and anticipation)	Short survey (pop- up window that will appear upon first access to the online catalogue- ISIA application)	1. Assess how ethical issues are addressed by consortium partner 2. Coordination and information exchange with WP1, WP2 to define ethical questionnaire	CoU ⁵		
Collect and exchange on ethical issues during TNA proposal preparation (for evaluation and anticipation) - detailed	Survey	Assess result Coordination and information exchange with WP1, WP2 to define ethical questionnaire			
⁵ RI access manager to verify answers suitability					
T5.1. Build a transdisciplinary community of users (CoU)					
One day liaising event – for new users' engagement, liaise, generate synergies (on e.g. guidelines, recommendations, common approaches, policy briefs + show project results) with initiatives identified under task 5.3.	Working groups on selected topics of interest to: - assess potential community of users; - importance of RIs service pipeline construction to boost AE transition	1. Identification & agreement with project partners of the most relevant initiatives (e.g., projects, networks) 2. Define the agenda in collaboration with AgroServ project partners 3. Invite potential participants and share technical details about events	Agroecology community (broad)	Around 4- 7 projects	Hybrid
Identification of the motivation and barriers of the AgroServ call for tender application procedure	Working session to evaluate the service provision process e.g., problem solution matrix, tree	1. Assess the CoU and services provided by RI 2. Selection of the most relevant CoU participants 3. Plan the session (invitations, role distribution, expected outputs)	RIs & CoU	20-40	Online
Generation of recommendations (road-mapping) to upscale the AgroServ service provision approach	Working session to evaluate impact of AgroServ actions & service pipeline (involvement) and recommendations generation	1. Selection of the most relevant CoU participants 2. Definition of the strategy to evaluate the impact 3. Plan the session (invitations, role distribution, expected outputs)			
⁴ RI and facility service providers and access managers					
⁵ RI access manager to verify answers suitability					

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Target group	# of participants	Format of involvement
Task 6.2. SoLabs and Virtual Learning Lab platform					
Assessment of the requirements and needs of the SoLabs platform	Working session (needs assessment tools e.g. participatory SWOT analysis, Delphi, value proposition canvas)	1. Identify the key user-group from which the requirements will be assessed 2. Invite the and agree on the roles and responsibilities	LL members ⁶	50	Virtual
Collection of end-users' feedback on platform functionalities	Evaluation survey	1. Develop the mock-up of the e-platform and share it with key-users group		100	Online
Task 6.3. Landscape & trends analysis					
Identification of potential stakeholders to participate in the participatory diagnosis	Prioritization tools e.g., elevator pitch, brainstorming	Map of extended network, via RI's contacts from different organizational types and levels (e.g. local, state, private)	LL members ⁷	50-100	Virtual
Assessment of the needs of the members participating in LL approach focused on the topics addressed by each RI	Working session - including needs assessment tools	Literature review of the state of the art of existing innovative initiatives needs and challenges towards AE transition			
Creation of a shared perspective and strategic priorities (adapted to local and LLs needs) by identifying the gap between services provided and end-users needs	Participatory diagnosis discussion cycle (virtually, include mapping problems and solutions demand by the LL audience)	Previous assessment of a) state of play of each RI service, b) potential contribution of each RI to LLs, c) Identify gaps vs end LL users' expectations			
Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Target group	# of participants	Format of involvement
Task 6.4. Establishing LLs and services demonstrations					
Identification of the potential stakeholders that can be engaged with through the different LL (5 countries)	Working session – identify the interest of the potential members to participate in LL and service demonstration using prioritisation tools	Assess the list of AgroServ stakeholders mapping performed under task 5.1. in the 5 Regions of interest	Potential LL members	30-50	Virtual
Selection of the demonstration: Identification and prioritization of the specific AE problems faced by LL (for RIs to propose solutions targeted to their needs) (MS6.2).	First discussion cycle (working sessions) using the online platform developed in T6.2. Tools – matchmaking, six thinking hats, speedboat, vision development	Assess the results of Task 6.3. and potential inputs from Task 6.3 and Task 6.2.	LL members		Virtual
⁶ with the LL orchestrator support					
⁷ extended network of RIs					

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Target group	# of participants	Format of involvement
Task 6.4. Establishing LLs and services demonstrations (cont)					
Demonstration of the application of a potential service performed at the premises of a specific installation of the LL organiser. Thus, fostering discussion and exchange on the potential outcome of the service provision	Second discussion cycle (working sessions) using on-site demonstration, vision development	First discussion cycle results analysed	LL members	80	In-person
Co-harmonization of LL methodologies to assess the suitability of the methodology on the one hand, and on the other hand the outcomes of the discussion cycles	Cross-learning meetings & online survey evaluation	Literature review on potential methodologies (T6.1)	LL managers, LL organisers and LL orchestrators	10	Virtual
Cross-evaluation of LL procedures to verify how the procedures and management of the LLs work (closely related to previous action)	Cross-learning meetings & online survey evaluation	Co-harmonization of LL methodologies performed	LL managers and LL organisers		
Task 6.5. ENoLL Accreditation					
Exchange of LL users' experiences regarding procedures, management and practices on LL implementation)	Discussion cycles: cross-learning virtual meetings + on-line surveys for evaluation/feedback in collaboration or as follow up of T6.1, T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4	Assess the running process of the LLs and collect feedback to evaluate the e-platform	LL members ⁶	around 80	Virtual, in person
Gather feedback from the community of users (LLs) to identify the barrier and drivers for scaling up the innovations developed by the RIs in the project calls for proposals	Working and discussion sessions: SWOT, Problem solving tool	Assess the implementation process of the LLs, collect feedback to evaluate the e-platform	LL members ⁶	80-100	Virtual
⁶ (with the LL orchestrator support) (with the LL orchestrator support)					
⁷ & extended network of RIs					

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Participants (target group)	number of participants	Format of involvement
Task 8.2. General exploitation, dissemination of results and outreach (M6-M60) & Task					
Thematic Webinar 1- Raise awareness on the AgroServ project & services; Involve the first round of stakeholders in the AgroServ project, as potential TNA service users	Livestream, recorded video and information to be disseminated on the appropriate media channels (e.g. video channel), Written (Q&A).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Build the webinar agenda & invite speakers 2. Prepare relevant communication materials 3. Identify potential participants and relevant institutions 4. Disseminate (social media, website, RIs, partners and AgroServ network) <p>=> <i>Details on the action plan and event checklist can be found in the Communication, dissemination, and Exploitation Plan</i></p>	CoU (open to all but target priority of Researchers) & Consortium partners	Open to anyone interested	On-line
Extra Webinar (optional) - In case not enough preproposals are presented in September (less than 20 preproposals) an additional Webinar will be organised					
Thematic Webinar 2- Two parts; 1) presentation & discussion of the first AgroServ Service provision; 2) Engage the second round of stakeholders as TNA users					
Thematic Webinar 3- Two parts; 1) presentation & discussion of the AgroServ Service provision; 2) Engage the third round of stakeholders as TNA users					
Thematic Webinar 4- - Two parts; 1) presentation & discussion of the AgroServ Service provision; 2) Engage the fourth round of stakeholders as TNA users	Interactive session, recorded video and information to be disseminated on the appropriate media channels (e.g. video channel)		CoU & Consortium partners		
AgroServ Conference 1- Foster exchange and Interaction among community of users and RIs to start the preparation of the TNA proposal (first call)	Working session - Brainstorming, Matchmaking, problem needs trees, evaluation questionnaire	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Programme preparation: agenda, speakers and working sessions dynamization (together with scientific committee) 2. Prepare relevant communication materials 3. Disseminate (social media, website, RIs, partners and AgroServ network) <p>=> <i>Details on the action plan and event checklist can be found in the Communication, dissemination, and Exploitation Plan</i></p>	CoU & Consortium partners	Open to anyone interested (max 100)	Hybrid

Engagement action / aim	Potential methodological approach*	previous/anticipatory actions	Participants (target group)	number of participants	Format of involvement
Task 8.2. General exploitation, dissemination of results and outreach (M6-M60) & Task					
AgroServ Conference 2- Engage the community of users & dissemination of the first TNA call results, discuss the contributions of AgroServ towards AE transition (including the initiatives we established links with)	Scientific/technical conference + Working sessions for application procedures and engagement support	1. Programme preparation: agenda, speakers and working sessions dynamization (together with scientific committee) 2. Prepare relevant communication materials 3. Disseminate (social media, website, RIs, partners and AgroServ network) => <i>Details on the action plan and event checklist can be found in the Communication, dissemination, and Exploitation Plan</i>	CoU & Consortium partners & Network	Open to anyone interested (max 100)	Hybrid
AgroServ extra Conference (optional) - half day scientific/technical event to show up results of services provision (e.g. experiments)	Working session				Online
AgroServ Conference 3- Results and planning of AgroServ future (long term sustainability)	Working session, recommendations on pathways towards sustainability and future steps of Agroecology transition		CoU & Consortium partners & Network (including policy makers)		Hybrid
Task 8.2. Communication towards policy makers					
Synthesis for policy makers 1- Discuss the preliminary data and evidences generated by AgroServ project for data-driven policy making	Working session in project conference where findings will be shown, potentially meeting with EU high level policy makers	1. Identification of the most relevant stakeholders 2. Work on policy briefs and/or white papers to be published 3. Define a dissemination plan with the relevant channels and events to present those briefs or reports	Policy makers	5-10 (potentially)	Online (in person if possible)
Synthesis for policy makers 2- Discuss the final achievements of AgroServ and its contribution towards AE transition					

Table 10 – Timeline of the AgroServ project actions that will require the involvement of project stakeholders

Tasks	Activity	22	2023				2024				2025				2026				2027		
		Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3																
T1.3	Consortium preparation - TNA preproposal																				
T1.3	Expression of interest preparation - TNA preproposal																				
T1.3	Finding targeted required services																				
T1.3	Stimulating and facilitating interdisciplinarity																				
T1.3	Full proposal preparation																				
T1.3	Assess support needs during implementation process																				
T1.3	Evaluate the process of AgroServ services application																				
T1.3	Share feedback to applicants																				
T2.2	Identify the thematic and scientific priorities																				
T2.3	Assess the service pipeline integration																				
T2.3	Profiling potential users interested in AgroServ services																				
T2.3	Gather feedback to evaluate services provision integration																				
T4.1	Feedback gathering - Evaluate the quality of AgroServ service provision																				
T4.1	Feedback gathering - Evaluate the ethical issues (proposal preparation)																				
T4.1	Detailed feedback gathering - Evaluate ethical issues (proposal preparation)																				
T5.1.	Event - liaising with other likewise initiatives																				
T5.1.	Assess motivation and barriers of the AgroServ services application procedure																				
T5.1.	Road-mapping to upscale the AgroServ service provision approach																				

	22	2023				2024				2025				2026				2027			
Tasks Activity	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3																	
T6.2. Assessment of the requirements and needs of the SoLabs platform																					
T6.2. Collection of end-users' feedback on platform functionalities																					
T6.3. Identification of potential stakeholders for the participatory diagnosis																					
T6.3. Assessment of the needs of the members participating in LL approach																					
T6.3. Creation of a shared perspective and strategic priorities																					
T6.4. Identification of stakeholders to be engaged in the different LL s																					
T6.4. Selection of the demonstrator																					
T6.4. Demonstration of the application of a potential AgroServ service																					
T6.4. Co-harmonization of LL methodologies																					
T6.4. Cross-harmonization of LL methodologies																					
T6.5. Exchange of LL users' experiences regarding procedures, management																					
T6.5. Gather feedback from the community of users (LLs)																					
T8.2. Thematic Webinar 1																					
T8.2. Extra (optional) Webinar																					
T8.2. Thematic Webinar 2																					
T8.2. Thematic Webinar 3																					
T8.2. Thematic Webinar 4																					
T8.2. AgroServ Conference 1																					
T8.2. AgroServ Conference 2																					
T8.2. AgroServ extra Conference (optional)																					
T8.2. AgroServ Conference 3																					

7. Evaluation of the engagement activities

The AgroServ project is committed to a genuine involvement of the community of users and other relevant stakeholders. Collecting feedback, gauging opinion and attitudes are essential, not only through WP4 (dedicated to collecting feedback from users and stakeholders) but also through the different work packages and activities in which stakeholders of the project are involved.

Different methods will be implemented including post-activity (e.g., webinar and conferences) feedback survey (e.g. on the quality of the provision of services, its integration and the process for application to the AgroServ services), brief interviews (testimonials), reflective discussions at project meetings to identify and learn from successful and less successful experiences. Specifically, a template to reflective evaluate the involvement process of the different stakeholders' types is here drafted to be performed after each activity that requires the active participation of any type of stakeholders (Annex 3).

A comprehensive review of these activities, with special focus on the LLs activities will be included in the D5.2. Reports of co-creation experiences where the suggestions of the stakeholder's engagement activities will be gathered and translated into tangible recommendations which are feasible for upscaling.

8. List of forums for communication and engagement

This section focuses on international and European events that could be of interest to the AgroServ project. This event list will be regularly updated, with the help of the 73 partners, including other relevant national, regional and local events.

X Agroecology International Congress

Type	Congress	Venue	Viseu, Portugal	Date	2-6 September 2024 (annual)
Organizer	Polytechnic Institute of Viseu				
Description					

This international annual congress seeks to generate a space for exchange and collective debate on the progress towards agroecological transition based on local food systems.

<http://events.ipv.pt/xcia/en/>

Forum for the Future of Agriculture (ForumforAg) Annual Conference

Type	Congress/Forum	Venue	Brussels (Belgium)	Date	28 March 23 (annual)
Organizer	Forum for the Future of Agriculture				
Description					

The Forum for the Future of Agriculture aims to debate sustainable agriculture and environmental challenges. Since 2008, the Forum is where agriculture and environment meet for an open dialogue, both online and in-person.

<https://forumforag.com/events/annual-conference-2023/>

4th International Conference on Plant Science and Agriculture

Type	Conference	Venue	Vienna, Austria (Hybrid)	Date	12-14 June, 2023 (annual)
-------------	------------	--------------	--------------------------	-------------	---------------------------

Organizer Allied Gathering

Description

The Conference encloses all the vital topics on Plant Science and focuses on recent research works in this field. It also provides a global network of eminent speakers, researchers, scientists, academicians, and professional related individuals.

[4th International Conference on Plant Science and Agriculture](#)

The circular economy in the context of a limited supply of biomass – ways forward to address biodiversity loss and climate change

Type	EU Circular Talks	Venue	tbc	Date	13 June 2023
-------------	-------------------	--------------	-----	-------------	--------------

Organizer EEA Sinnen-Wandel Sitra CERDI

Description

Some circular economy practitioners believe that switching to biomass is the best way to implement the circular economy. However, the circular economy is not synonymous with bioeconomy. The circular economy is about retaining the value of materials for as long as possible, and consequently it cannot be achieved simply by adding more and more primary biomass to the economy. Demand for biomass is increasing rapidly yet supply is limited, leading to problems for climate and biodiversity.

[The circular economy in the context of a limited supply of biomass – ways forward to address biodiversity loss and climate change](#)

Sustainable Foods Summit Europe

Type	Summit	Venue	Amsterdam (Netherlands)	Date	15-16 June 2023 (annual)
-------------	--------	--------------	-------------------------	-------------	--------------------------

Organizer IFOAM Organics Europe

Description

Since 2009, the Sustainable Foods Summit has been discussing leading issues the food industry faces concerning sustainability and eco-labels, such as Organic, Fair Trade, Rainforest Alliance, etc. The aim of the Sustainable Foods Summit is to explore new horizons for eco-labels and sustainability in the food industry by discussing key industry issues

[Sustainable Foods Summit](#)

5th IEEE International Workshop on Smart Circular Economy

Type	Workshop	Venue	Paphos (Cyprus)	Date	19 - 21 Jun 2023 (annual)
-------------	----------	--------------	-----------------	-------------	---------------------------

Organizer IEEE Bournemouth University

Description

This workshop focuses on the role of ICT as an enabler for Circular Economy. It brings together scientists, as well as relevant stakeholders from the industry and local communities to share and exchange their experiences, discuss challenges, and report state-of-the-art and in-progress research on ICT and Circular Economy

[5th IEEE International Workshop on Smart Circular Economy](#)

3rd European Rural Geographies Conference

Type	Conference	Venue	Groningen/Netherlands.	Date	June 23-26, 2023 (annual)
Organizer	Faculty of Spatial Sciences, University of Groningen				
Description	<p>This conference brings forward new research questions and asks for new approaches, both in terms of theoretical perspectives and in terms of empirics, on topics such as population developments, socio-spatial inequalities, governance and policies, economic challenges, quality of life, smart villages, landscape transitions, rural entrepreneurship, agricultural transformations, rural housing, energy transitions and climate change adaptation.</p> <p>3rd European Rural Geographies Conference</p>				

3rd Global Conference on Agriculture

Type	Conference	Venue	Amsterdam (Netherlands)	Date	24 - 25 June 2023 (annual)
Organizer	STECOF				
Description	<p>Ecosystem-level conservation, plant genomics, farm management, and artificial intelligence in farming – are just a few examples of topics that the international agriculture conference will cover. Agriculture plays a central role in global health and development. As new technologies emerge, the field faces unprecedented opportunities, and, if utilized wisely, can solve problems on a global scale. However, the field faces many issues that must be addressed through careful, targeted research.</p> <p>Global Conference on Agriculture</p>				

XXIXth European Society for Rural Sociology Congress "*Crises and the futures of rural areas*"

Type	Congress	Venue	Rennes, France	Date	July 3 – 7, 2023
Organizer	L'Institut Agro				
Description	<p>This conference explores the impact of various crises on rural areas and examines the ways in which rural areas are perceived and imagined. Additionally, the conference examines the potential futures and alternative trajectories for rural areas in areas such as food production, health, energy, community, planning, tourism, and technology in the context of crises.</p> <p>XXIXth European Society for Rural Sociology Congress Crises and the futures of rural areas</p>				

26th European Seminar on Extension & Education - Sustainability transitions of agriculture and the transformation of education and advisory services convergence or divergence?

Type	Seminar	Venue	Toulouse	Date	10-13 July 2023 (biennial)
-------------	---------	--------------	----------	-------------	----------------------------

Organizer INRAE

Description

This seminar aims at supporting discussion between science and practice. Hence, it is open to a diversity of contributions, both academic and practical. It gathers and contrast experiences and findings from all European countries, but also between Europe and other contexts in the global North and global South. The seminar has led to the publication of several special issues in the Journal of Agricultural Extension and Education and other academic publications.

[26th European Seminar on Extension & Education - \(inrae.fr\)](https://www.inrae.fr/en/26th-european-seminar-on-extension-education)

APDR - Sustainability Development Challenges of Territories in Contexts of Uncertainties due to External Shocks and Risks

Type	Congress	Venue	Braga, Portugal	Date	29-21 - July 2023
-------------	----------	--------------	-----------------	-------------	-------------------

Organizer University of Minho

Description

The overall aim of this conference is to bring ideas, theoretical approaches and examples of potential solutions to territorial bottlenecks and social and development difficulties.

[30th ADPR Congress](https://www.adpr-congress.com/)

IV Congresso Internacional. 6 - Food sovereignty - production and supply dynamics in the long run

Type	Congress	Venue	Coimbra, Portugal	Date	6-7-8 Sept 23
-------------	----------	--------------	-------------------	-------------	---------------

Organizer Rural RePort and SEHA

Description

The conference aims to explore the dynamics of production, transaction, transformation, storage, and consumption of food products and promote interpretations anchored in historical knowledge. It seeks to understand the historical context of food sovereignty and examine the connections between local communities, territories, and institutions in the development of agricultural and food strategies. The conference encourages interdisciplinary discussions and welcomes specialists from various disciplines and historical periods

[IV International Congress on Agricultural and Food Challenges](https://www.ivcongresso.com/)

OpenLivingLab Days 2023

Type	Workshop	Venue	Barcelona, Spain	Date	21-13Sept 23
-------------	----------	--------------	------------------	-------------	--------------

Organizer European Network of Living Labs

Description

OLLDD will not only gather Living Lab professionals, changemakers, shapers, entrepreneurs, and academics but will also provide a space to develop new ideas and form partnerships. Professionals will join to share their thoughts and experiences on the most pressing matters facing our living environments today.

<https://openlivinglabdays.com/>

Funded by
the European Union

ALL-Ready and AE4EU joint final conference

Type	Conference	Venue	Brussels	Date	27 Sept 23
Organizer	AllReady and AE4EU project				
Description	<p>The one-day conference will shed light on how the two projects paved the way for a European Network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Both projects will feature stories from the field, pilot networks, and local stakeholders. Experiences from involved Living Labs and Research Infrastructures will give practical insights.</p> <p>https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/all-ready-final-conference.html</p> <p>http://agrosym.ues.rs.ba/</p>				

XIV International Agriculture Symposium “AGROSYM 2023” Jahorina

Type	Conference	Venue	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Date	5-8 October 2023 (annual)
Organizer	Faculty of Agriculture University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina; Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia; CIHEAM - Bari, Italy				
Description	<p>AGROSYM international scientific discussion on agriculture, food, rural development, environment and forestry. It represents a good opportunity to exchange ideas, to strengthen existing and to create new academic networks, and to foster dialogue between the academia, public institutions, the private sector and civil society organizations on the recent global and regional trends in the agro-food sector. Multidisciplinary results reported during AGROSYM will contribute to the dissemination of knowledge and good practices to all actors of the agro-food chain (e.g. farmers, extension agents, researchers, policy makers) as well as the general public about the importance of agriculture and food science.</p> <p>http://agrosym.ues.rs.ba/</p>				

FoodSHIFT 2030 Policy Conference

Type	Conference	Venue	To Confirm	Date	26-Oct-2023
Organizer	IFOAM Organics Europe				
Description	<p>The final conference of the FoodSHIFT2030 project aimed at policy makers and open to consortium members, associations and policy makers to discuss how the achievements of the FoodSHIFT2030 project can be applied to guide the further development of food related policies within the EU</p> <p>https://foodshift2030.eu/event/foodshift_2030-vision/</p>				

Organic Innovation Days 2023

Type	Conference	Venue	Brussels (Belgium)	Date	25-26 Oct 2023
-------------	------------	--------------	--------------------	-------------	----------------

Organizer IFOAM Organics Europe

Description

Under the theme “Citizen-driven transformation of European food systems“, this conference will explore the role of citizens in making our food systems more sustainable, as well as the potential of organic to contribute to long-term food security

<https://www.organicseurope.bio/news/save-the-date-organic-innovation-days-2023-on-citizen-driven-transformation-of-european-food-systems/>

Agroecology Europe Forum 2023

Type	Congress/Forum	Venue	Hungary	Date	16 - 18 Nov, 2023
-------------	----------------	--------------	---------	-------------	-------------------

Organizer Agroecology Europe AEEU

Description

The Agroecology Europe Forum is a 3-day in-person event gathering people from all over Europe and beyond to meet in dialogue and discuss some of the most pressing issues and present solutions for today's food systems.

<https://www.agroecology-europe.org/call-for-proposals-forum2023/>

10. Conclusions

This deliverable develops guidelines for engaging Stakeholders and users in the activities of the AgroServ consortium. It provides the consortium with a large database of more than 100 stakeholders that can be part of the future engaged community of AgroServ services users. Additionally, this pool of stakeholders can also act as catalysers to engage other stakeholders in this project.

The document also offers a framework for enhancing participatory and co-creation processes in the implementation of the different AgroServ activities. It outlines not only specific methods and tools for the engagement of stakeholders but also essential ingredients to ensure that the proposed AgroServ service pipeline are co-designed and co-developed with the community of users and tailored to the final users' needs.

RIs services and installation access managers are key actors on the engagement process. They play a major role in ensuring the success of a two-way dialogue and interaction with stakeholders. They should be active on mobilising the potential community of users for efficient service provision under TNA calls. This document can be employed as a guide in the development of collaborative proposal that could support the sustainable transition towards agroecology.

While this document proposes a common framework for stakeholders' engagement, further updates and adaptations might be performed, based on specific needs, to improve consortium capacities for stakeholders' mobilisation and engagement.

11. References

- Boger J, Jackson P, Mulvenna M, Sixsmith J, Sixsmith A, Mihailidis A, et al. (2017). Principles for fostering the transdisciplinary development of assistive technologies. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*. 12:480–90.
- Gliessman, S. (2016). Transforming food systems with agroecology. *Agroecology and sustainable food systems*, 40(3), 187-189.
- Grigorovich A, Fang ML, Sixsmith J, Kontos P. (2019). Defining and evaluating the effectiveness of transdisciplinary research in aging and technology. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*. 14:533–42.
- Frascati, M. (2015). Guidelines for collecting and reporting data on research and experimental development. URL: <http://www.oecd.org/sti/frascati-manual-2015-9789264239012-en.htm>.
- HLPE. (2019). Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition. A report by the High-Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security. Rome: FAO.
- Kambil, A., Friesen G.B., and Sundaram A. (1999). Co-creation: A New Source of Value. *Accenture Outlook*, 2.
- Schmitz, K., Mahapatra, R., & Nerur, S. (2018). User engagement in the era of hybrid agile methodology. *IEEE software*, 6(4), 32-40.
- Oh, J., & Sundar, S. S. (2016). User engagement with interactive media: A communication perspective. *Why engagement matters: Cross-disciplinary perspectives of user engagement in digital media*, 177-198.
- Rita Costa and Barbara Pintar (2020). Communication Toolkit for European Research Infrastructure. RI-VIS project grant agreement NO824063.
- Kujala, S. (2003). User involvement: a review of the benefits and challenges. *Behaviour & information technology*, 22(1), 1-16. DOI: 10.1080/01449290301782
- Ralph N. and Vogel N. (2018). Facilitation toolkit: Tips and tricks for participatory and empowering facilitation. *Transgender Europe (TGEU)*
- Mambrini-Doudet, M., Gascuel, C., Gödel, B., McKhann, H. (2021). D1.1 Reference document with key concepts: Vision for building the network of living labs and research infrastructures for agroecology transition. ALL-Ready Deliverable.
- Hagy, S., Morrison, G. M., and Elfstrand, P. (2016) Chapter 13 - Co-creation in Living Labs in *Living Labs* ed. Keyson, D.V., Guerra-Santin, O. and Lockton, D. Springer International Publishing ISBN: 978-3-319-33526-1
- Ballon, P., Pierson, J., Delaere, S. (2005) Test and Experimentation Platforms for Broadband Innovation: Examining European Practice. *Studies on Media, Information and Telecommunication (SMIT) — Interdisciplinary Institute for BroadBand Technology (IBBT), Vrije Universiteit Brussel*. Belgium: Brussels. pp. 7–9.

Funded by
the European Union

Kreiling, L. and Paunov, C. (2021). Knowledge co-creation in the 21st century: A cross-country experience-based policy report. OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 115, OECD Publishing, Paris.

Puerari, E., De Koning, J. I. J. C., Von Wirth, T., Karré, P. M. 3, Mulder, I. J. and Loorbach, D. A. (2018). Co-Creation Dynamics in Urban Living Labs. Sustainability 2018, 10(6), 1893;

Alvarez, S., Douthwaite, B., Thiele, G., Mackay, R., Córdoba, D., & Tehelen, K. (2010). Participatory impact pathways analysis: a practical method for project planning and evaluation. Development in Practice, 20(8), 946-958.

Brouwer et al., 2019. MSP toolkit Wageningen

Funded by
the European Union

Annexes

Annex 1 – AgroServ stakeholders: Potential community of users

POTENTIAL COMMUNITY OF USERS				
N	Institution Name	Web	Stakeholder Type	Geographical scope
1	A.R.A. Lombardia	LINK	Associations and organizations	Local
2	Aarhus University	LINK	Scientific community	European
3	Agia Basilicata	LINK	Associations and organizations	Local
4	Agricultural Association of The Czech Republic	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
5	Agricultural Industries Confederation	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
6	AgriFood - Economics Center	LINK	Scientific community	National
7	Agri-Food - Environment and Renewable Energy Centre (EREC)	LINK	Scientific community	International
8	Agro School for Life (ISARA)	LINK	Scientific community	International
9	Agroecology and Organic Agriculture Living Lab (LLAEBIO) - ILVO	LINK	Networks	Local
10	Agrofood-BIC	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
11	Agroscope	LINK	Scientific community	European
12	Andalusian Agency of Agriculture and Fisheries (AGAPA)	LINK	Public sector	Local
13	Apheabio	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
14	Arla Foods UK Plc	LINK	Large Agribusiness	National
15	Association Of Farmers of The Czech Republic	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
16	Association Of Fruit and Vegetable Producers of Almería (COEXPHAL)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
17	Autonomous University of Barcelona	LINK	Scientific community	European
18	BAGAP Research Unit: Biodiversity, Agroecology, And Landscape Management	LINK	Scientific community	National
19	BARILLA	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
20	Basque Institute for Agricultural Research and Development	LINK	Scientific community	National
21	Bayer Cropscience	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
22	Bioazul	LINK	SME Agribusiness	International
23	Biology Department, National Kapodistrian University of Athens	LINK	Scientific community	European
24	Biowallonie	LINK	Large Agribusiness	Local
25	Bonarea	LINK	Large Agribusiness	National

Funded by
the European Union

26	Bonifiche Ferraresi	LINK	Large Agribusiness	Other - specify
27	CEITEC Masaryk University	LINK	Scientific community	International
28	Central Inspectorate for the Protection of Quality and Fraud Repression of Agri-Food Products (ICQRF)	LINK	Public sector	National
29	Centre For Aquaculture Research, ITACYL	LINK	Scientific community	European
30	Centre For Gene and Cellular Therapies in The Treatment Of Cancer (Oncogen)	LINK	Scientific community	European
31	CIA Italian Farmers Association	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
32	CLAN Cluster Agrifood	LINK	Networks	National
33	Cluster Lucano Bioeconomy	LINK	Networks	Local
34	Complutense University of Madrid	LINK	Scientific community	European
35	Confagricultura	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
36	Conservatoire De L'espace Littoral Et Des Rivages Lacustres	LINK	Public sector	National
37	Consortium For Technological Innovation (DINTEC)	LINK	Networks	National
38	CREDA - Center for Agro-Food Economics and Development	LINK	Scientific community	Local
39	Cyprus Marine & Maritime Institute - CCMI	LINK	Scientific community	European
40	Czech-Moravian Dairy Association	LINK	Associations and organizations	European
41	Czech-Moravian Society of Livestock Breeders	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
42	Dale Farm Ltd	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
43	Dunarea De Jos, University of Galati (UGAL)	LINK	Scientific community	International
44	ELGO - Veterinary Research Institute Greek Agricultural Organization Demeter	LINK	Scientific community	European
45	Estonian University of Life Sciences	LINK	Scientific community	International
46	European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF)	LINK	Associations and organizations	European
47	European Infrastructure Project	LINK	Scientific community	European
48	European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)	LINK	Associations and organizations	International
49	EXO Research	LINK	Networks	National
50	Extremadura Scientific and Technological Research Center (CICYTEX)	LINK	Scientific community	Local
51	Fablab Lazio	LINK	Public sector	Local
52	Federalimentare	LINK	Associations and organizations	European
53	Federation of Italian Agronomy (FIDAF)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National

54	Federation of the Food and Drink Industries of The Czech Republic (FFDI)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
55	Federbio	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
56	Fibl - Research Institute of Organic Agriculture	LINK	Scientific community	European
57	Food And Agriculture Organization of The United Nations (FAO)	LINK	Associations and organizations	International
58	Forumoceano	LINK	Networks	European
59	Global Long-Term Agricultural Experiment Network (GLTEN)	LINK	Networks	International
60	Graham's Family Dairy	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
61	Grup Bonarea	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
62	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research	LINK	Scientific community	International
63	Hellenic Mediterranean University	LINK	Scientific community	European
64	Hkscan	LINK	Large Agribusiness	European
65	Honkajoki Ltd	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
66	IBBA Institute of Agricultural Biology and Biotechnology (CNR)	LINK	Scientific community	Local
67	IFAPA-El Toruño	LINK	Scientific community	European
68	INAGRO - Research & Advice in Agriculture and Horticulture	LINK	Scientific community	European
69	Institute For Food and Agricultural Research and Technology	LINK	Scientific community	European
70	Institute of Aquaculture Torre De La Sal-CSIC	LINK	Scientific community	European
71	Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia-CSIC	LINK	Scientific community	European
72	Institute of Marine Sciences-CSIC	LINK	Scientific community	European
73	Institute of Physico-Chemical Biology - CNRS - Sorbonne University	LINK	Scientific community	European
74	International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements - IFOAM	LINK	Associations and organizations	International
75	IRTA Sant Carles De La Ràpita	LINK	Scientific community	European
76	Italian Association of The Olive Oil Industry (ASSITOIL)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
77	Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ICESP)	LINK	Networks	National
78	Jaen University	LINK	Scientific community	National
79	Latvia University of Life Sciences And Technologies	LINK	Scientific community	International
80	Lazioinnova	LINK	Public sector	Local
81	Leibniz Centre For Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) E.V. Müncheberg	LINK	Scientific community	National
82	Lincoln University	LINK	Scientific community	International
83	Linking Environment and Farming	LINK	Associations and organizations	Local

84	Madrid Institute for Research and Rural Development, Agrarian and Food (Agrolab Madrid)	LINK	Public sector	Local
85	Max Planck Institute for Plant Breeding Research	LINK	Scientific community	International
86	Mértola Agroecology Center	LINK	Networks	Local
87	Metameta Anatolia	LINK	SME Agribusiness	International
88	Müller Milk & Ingredients	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
89	National Institute for Research and Development of Isotopic And Molecular Technologies (INCDTIM)	LINK	Scientific community	International
90	Naturescot	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
91	Nordkalk	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
92	Nourish Scotland	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
93	Ocean4Biotech Network in Marine Biotechnology	LINK	Scientific community	European
94	Oxford University	LINK	Scientific community	National
95	Pablo De Olavide University of Seville	LINK	Scientific community	International
96	Politehnica University of Bucharest (UPB)	LINK	Scientific community	International
97	Polytechnic University of Valencia	LINK	Scientific community	European
98	Port of Antwerp (POA)	LINK	Scientific community	European
99	Portuguese Association of Aquaculturists	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
100	PRO-BIO Union Of Organic Farmers	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
101	Progressive Farming Trust Ltd	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
102	Qualivita Foundation	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
103	Regional Agency for the Development and Innovation of Agriculture of Lazio (ARSIAL)	LINK	Public sector	Local
104	Research Centre in Biodiversity and Genetic Resources	LINK	Scientific community	International
105	Research For Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE)	LINK	Scientific community	European
106	Research Institute for Analytical Instrumentation (ICIA)	LINK	Scientific community	International
107	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (OMKI)	LINK	Scientific community	European
108	Rikolto	LINK	Associations and organizations	International
109	Ruralis - Institute for Rural and Regional Research	LINK	Scientific community	National
110	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies (SSSA)	LINK	Scientific community	International
111	Santiago De Compostela University	LINK	Scientific community	European

112	Sapienza University of Rome	LINK	Scientific community	European
113	Saputo Dairy Ltd	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
114	Soil Association Scotland	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
115	Soilfood Ltd	LINK	SME Agribusiness	European
116	Spanish Professional Association of Organic Production (ECOVALIA)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
117	Spanish Society of Organic Farming/Agroecology (SEAE)	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
118	Special Agency of the Chamber of Commerce of Rome for the development and promotion of the agri-food system and the management of the Commodity Exchange (AGROCAMERA)	LINK	Public sector	Local
119	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)	LINK	Scientific community	International
120	Tecnoalimenti	LINK	Networks	National
121	The James Hutton Institute	LINK	Scientific community	International
122	The James Hutton Institute - Social, Economic, and Geographical Sciences	LINK	Scientific community	National
123	The Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry	LINK	Scientific community	International
124	The National Institute of Research - Development for Machines and Installations Designed for Agriculture And Food Industry (INMA)	LINK	Scientific community	European
125	The Research Institute of The University of Bucharest (ICUB)	LINK	Scientific community	European
126	The University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine Cluj-Napoca (USAMV Cluj)	LINK	Scientific community	International
127	Union of Consumers	LINK	Associations and organizations	National
128	University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest	LINK	Scientific community	European
129	University of Almería	LINK	Scientific community	European
130	University of Barcelona	LINK	Scientific community	European
131	University of Bari Aldo Moro	LINK	Scientific community	European
132	University of Bonn	LINK	Scientific community	National
133	University of Cadiz	LINK	Scientific community	European
134	University of Florence	LINK	Scientific community	International
135	University of Glasgow	LINK	Scientific community	International
136	University of Granada	LINK	Scientific community	European
137	University of Granada	LINK	Scientific community	Local

Funded by
the European Union

138	University of Helsinki (UH)	LINK	Scientific community	National
139	University of Helsinki (UH)	LINK	Scientific community	National
140	University of Hohenheim	LINK	Scientific community	International
141	University of Las Palmas De Gran Canaria	LINK	Scientific community	European
142	University of Life Sciences Timisoara (USVT)	LINK	Scientific community	International
143	University of Malaga	LINK	Scientific community	European
144	University of Molise (UNIMOL)	LINK	Scientific community	National
145	University of Murcia	LINK	Scientific community	European
146	University of Naples Federico II	LINK	Scientific community	European
147	University of Nottingham	LINK	Scientific community	International
148	University of Parma	LINK	Scientific community	European
149	University of Pisa	LINK	Public sector	National
150	University of Reading	LINK	Scientific community	International
151	University of Siena	LINK	Scientific community	European
152	University of Turin	LINK	Scientific community	Local
153	Valio Group	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
154	Vallefiorita	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National
155	VIB-UGent Center for Plant Systems Biology	LINK	Scientific community	International
156	Vision On Technology for A Better World (VITO)	LINK	Scientific community	European
157	Vytautas Magnus University	LINK	Scientific community	International
158	Wageningen Plant Research	LINK	Scientific community	International
159	Yara	LINK	Large Agribusiness	International
160	Yeo Valley Organic Limited	LINK	SME Agribusiness	National

Funded by
the European Union

OTHER STAKEHOLDERS (for liaison, communication and outreach purposes)				
N	Institution Name	Web	Stakeholder Type	Geographical scope
1	Confederazione Nazionale Coltivatori Diretti (Coldiretti)	LINK	Associations & organizations	National
2	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners (MTK)	LINK	Associations & organizations	National
3	European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives (CopaCogeca)	LINK	Associations & organizations	European
4	European Plant Science Organisatio (EPSO)	LINK	Associations & organizations	International
5	International Plant Phenotyping Network (IPPN)	LINK	Associations & organizations	International
6	Agroecology Europe	LINK	Associations & organizations	European
7	AgriCord	LINK	Associations & organizations	International
8	Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG)	LINK	Associations & organizations	European
9	ProAgria	LINK	Associations & organizations	Local
10	European LandOwners Organization (ELO)	LINK	Associations & organizations	European
11	European Council of young farmers (CEJA)	LINK	Associations & organizations	European
12	French Committee of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)	LINK	Associations & organizations	International
13	Banco Alimentare	LINK	Associations & organizations	National

Annex 2 – Participatory methods and tools

Data collection and data sharing

Surveys

Aim? Gather structured information and feedback from a target group

How it works? Surveys involve the use of structured questionnaires to gather statistically useful information (e.g feedback, opinions) from the community of users. When properly constricted and administered, questionnaires become a useful instrument by which statements can be made about specific groups or people or entire populations.

When to use it? Questionnaires can be used to collect feedback, assess partner satisfaction, gather opinions on project outcomes, or gather specific information related to project objectives. Different online tools can be applied for online surveys (table 2).

Advantages:	Limitations:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Allows for efficient data collection from a large number of participants.• Provides a standardized approach to gather information and feedback.• Enables the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Limited opportunity for real-time discussion or clarification of responses.• Relies on participants' willingness to complete and provide accurate responses• May require careful design and piloting to ensure the clarity and validity of the questions.

Tips

- Write concise, clear, simple questions in a simple language for ease of understanding
- Prevent questionnaire fatigue by don't surveying too often
- Make your questions really relevant and eliminate unsuitable or redundant questions.
- Prevent time consuming questionnaires to enhance response rate completeness
- Avoid as much as possible open questions to ease the analysis of data. Instead set categorical answers through e.g. multiple choice answer,

Table 2.- Comparison Table of Tools for online- surveys.

Survey Tool	Participants allowed	Specific functionalities (Added Value)
Slido	Up to 100, 3 polls per event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live Questions & Answers to quickly evaluate and assess interest, discussion topics, Polls • It can be used at the beginning or end of the working sessions • Slido is a great tool for Q&A sessions, particularly in large meetings or webinars. The participants can ask questions in real-time without interrupting the speaker, and others can upvote the questions they find most relevant. This allows the meeting facilitator to prioritize and address the most pressing questions. Slido can also be used for live polls during the meeting to get quick feedback.
Google Forms	Unlimited	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google Forms can be used when you need to collect detailed responses from the participants, either before or after the meeting or working session e.g. to gather agenda items from the participants before the meeting or to collect feedback on the meeting itself or to gather more complex ideas that require thoughtful responses
Survey Monkey	Unlimited, 10 questions per survey, View 10 responses per survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It provides advanced question types • It is useful for comprehensive surveys that might be too long or complex for a meeting setting. You can use Survey Monkey to gather pre-meeting information such as participants' background information, specific interests, or preferences for meeting structure. Post-meeting, you can use it for a detailed evaluation of the meeting or to collect further input on the discussion topics
Mentimeter	Unlimited audience and presentations, Up to 2 question slides, Up to 5 quiz slides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Powerful tool for real-time interaction during a meeting. It allows you to create fun and engaging presentations with live polls, quizzes, word clouds, and other interactive elements. It can be used in meeting to encourage participation, check the understanding of the participants, or generate discussion. For instance, you could use a word cloud to gather everyone's thoughts on a particular topic and display the results live during the meeting

More information?

- Vannieuwenborg, F., & Vanthienen, J. (2019). A Survey of Online Survey Tools: Features, Issues, and Selection Criteria. *International Journal of Business Process Integration and Management*, 10(2), 133-148. DOI: 10.1504/IJBPIIM.2019.10019862
- Goosen, M., et al. (2021). Online Surveys in Education Research: An Analysis of Survey Tools, Features, and Applications. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 53(2), 188-207. DOI: 10.1080/15391523.2020.1867919

Interviews

Aim? Gather detailed insights, experiences, and feedback from a target group

How it works? Interviews involve one-on-one or small group discussions with the stakeholders of interest. These discussions can be conducted in person, over the phone, or through video conferencing platforms.

When to use it? Interviews facilitate in-depth discussions, sharing of experiences, and exchange of project results. They allow for a more personalized and nuanced understanding of partners' perspectives, enabling the identification of challenges, success stories, and areas for improvement.

<i>Advantages:</i>	<i>Limitations:</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides rich qualitative data and insights into partner experiences and perceptions. • Allows for open-ended questioning and exploration of diverse viewpoints. • Facilitates the establishment of rapport and trust between the project representative and partners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-consuming, particularly when conducting multiple interviews. • Requires skilled interviewers to facilitate productive discussions. • Findings may be subjective and influenced by the interviewer's biases or interpretations.

Tips

- Identify well when they are essential – testimonials to promote the use of AgroServ services
- Prepare in advance: Know what information you are seeking and prepare a list of relevant questions
- Create a comfortable atmosphere: Make sure the interviewee feels comfortable to share their insights honestly
- Be flexible: Be prepared to deviate from your prepared questions based on the interviewee's responses

More information?

- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, I. S. (2011). Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data. sage.
- Seidman, I. (2006). Interviewing as qualitative research: A guide for researchers in education and the social sciences. Teachers college press.

Focus groups/ Working sessions

Aim? gain insight into the experiences and perspectives of various stakeholders

How it works? Focus groups involve gathering a small group of actors to engage in a guided discussion on specific project topics or outcomes. A facilitator leads the session, encouraging participants to share their opinions, experiences while promoting group interaction and collaboration.

When to use it? Focus groups provide an interactive platform for consortium partners to explore project results, share insights, and collectively analyze information. They foster open dialogue, surface different perspectives, and generate in-depth qualitative data.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allows for group dynamics and interaction, promoting synergy among participants. • Facilitates the exploration of shared experiences and collective sense-making. • Provides an opportunity to delve into complex issues and identify common patterns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires skilled facilitation to manage group dynamics and ensure equal participation. • Findings may be influenced by dominant voices within the focus group. • Representativeness of the group's opinions needs careful consideration.

Tips

- Ensure diversity: The more diverse the group, the broader the perspectives will be.
- Facilitate effectively: A good facilitator guides discussions, ensuring everyone's voice is heard.
- Set rules: Establish the ground rules and stick to them.

More information?

- Morgan, D. L., Krueger, R. A., & King, J. A. (1998). The focus group guidebook. Sage.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012). Qualitative research design: An interactive approach. Sage publications.

Testimonials

Aim? Get positive feedback from users to build trust and credibility among the potential community of users

How it works? It is a short statement that describes how a product or service worked for a user's that has benefited from or experienced success

When to use it? To communicate, raise awareness and promote the possibilities and capabilities of the project

Tips

- Try to select the most successful story (user)
- Try to use the result of the process from different view points
- Show the specific application of the product or service

Facilitating connection among the group

Icebreakers activities

Aim? Break down initial barriers, create a sense of belonging, and set a conducive tone for further discussions and collaboration

How it works? They are generally performed at of the meeting or working session to allow everyone to know who is in the group. involve introductory questions, team-building exercises, or interactive games that promote engagement, conversation, and connection among participants. Examples of ice-breaking exercises can be found at Ralph and Vogel (2018).

When to use it? At the beginning of meetings, workshops, training sessions, or any gathering where participants may not be familiar with each other. They are particularly effective when participants come from diverse backgrounds or disciplines or when there is a need to create a cohesive and inclusive environment.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helps create a relaxed and welcoming atmosphere for participants. • Encourages interaction & active participation from the start. • Builds rapport, trust, and a sense of community among participants. • Fosters a positive and inclusive environment for conversations and discussions. • Enhances engagement, creativity, and collaboration among participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time constraints may limit the depth of ice breaker activities • Participants with different comfort levels may feel hesitant or uncomfortable with certain activities • Ice breakers may not suit all personality types or cultural contexts • Overuse or inappropriate choice of ice breakers may lead to disengagement or loss of focus • Effectiveness may vary depending on the facilitator's skills and the group dynamics

Tips:

- Relevant to audience: Choose activities that are relevant and appropriate for the group.
- Engage everyone: The activities should be inclusive and get everyone involved.
- Set the tone: Use icebreakers to set a positive tone for the meeting or session.
- Keep it short: Icebreakers should be brief and not take up too much of the meeting time.

More information?

- Barnett, M. A., et al. (2014). The Impact of Icebreaker Activities on Student Engagement in Online Learning. *Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 10(4), 507-520.
- Miller, M. T. (2012). The Use of Ice Breaker Activities in Online Learning: An Exploratory Study. *Online Journal of Distance Learning Administration*, 15(2).

Energizers

Aim? Re-energize participants, increase focus, and promote active engagement during meetings, workshops, or other gatherings.

How it works? Energizers are brief activities or exercises often involve physical movement, interactive games, or mental stimulation to awaken participants' energy levels and encourage a renewed sense of participation. Examples of energizer exercises can be found at Ralph and Vogel (2018).

When to use it? Energizers can be used at any point during a meeting, workshop, or training session when participants may be experiencing fatigue, a decline in focus, or reduced engagement. They are particularly effective when there is a need to shift the participants' mindset, or enhance collaboration and creativity. Energizers help maintain a dynamic and positive atmosphere, fostering continued engagement in conversations and discussions.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breaks up monotony, enhances focus and creates a lively and engaging environment. • Encourages team bonding, cooperation, and a positive group dynamic. • Boosts creativity, problem-solving, and idea generation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time constraints may limit the duration and scope of energizers. • Participants' comfort levels and physical abilities may vary, impacting their participation. • Some individuals may find certain energizers unappealing or distracting.

Tips

- Match the energy level: Choose activities that will appropriately raise the group's energy.
- Be conscious of time: Energizers should be quick, not drawn-out.
- Be flexible: Have a few options ready, and choose one based on the group's mood and needs.
- Overuse or improper choice of energizers may disrupt the flow of discussions.

More information?

- Bergman, M. E., et al. (2020). Energetic Energizers: The Effects of Short Exercise Breaks on Employee Energy, Work Engagement, and Job Performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 105(5), 557-571. DOI: 10.1037/apl0000470

Ideas sharing and definition

Brainstorming

Aim? Facilitate the exploration of a subject, generation of ideas

How it works? These tools provide a structured approach to idea generation by promoting a free-flowing and non-judgmental environment. Participants can contribute their thoughts, suggestions, and creative solutions related to a specific topic or problem. The tools often employ techniques such as mind mapping, idea clustering, and voting to organize and prioritize the generated ideas.

When to use it? They are particularly effective when the aim is to generate a large number of ideas, encourage collaboration and innovation, and foster equal participation among group members. Brainstorming tools can be employed during the early stages of a project to explore different perspectives, identify potential challenges, and develop creative solutions.

Another brainstorming version called “**Walt Disney Method**” (Dilts, 1994) method allows for a more practice thinking. Participants assume three roles 1) The dreamer: represents the vision and creates ideas. 2) The realist: focuses on the feasibility of the ideas. 3) The critic: is the devil's advocate and sees only the risks and weaknesses of the idea.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stimulates innovative thinking and the exploration of alternative solutions by providing a structured approach • Promotes equal participation and engagement among group members. • Facilitates the organization, clustering, and prioritization of ideas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential dominance of certain individuals, hindering the input from others. • Time constraints may limit the depth and breadth of idea generation. • May require skilled facilitation to maintain focus and drive productive discussions.

Tips

- Sticky notes can be used for ideas sharing – keep one idea per sticky note
- Quantity over quality: The aim is to generate as many ideas as possible; refinement comes later.

- Mix individual and group brainstorming: Some individuals might feel more comfortable generating ideas alone while others in group
- Time-box your sessions and try to keep it short: This encourages focus and productivity

More information?

- Paulus, P. B., & Nijstad, B. A. (2003). Group creativity: Innovation through collaboration. Oxford University Press.
- Huckfeldt, R., & Steenbergen, M. R. (1995). Discussant effects in small groups: A social identity model of brainstorming. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 31(4), 299-316. DOI: 10.1006/jesp.1995.1009

Word coffee

Aim? To informally collect ideas on a topic of mutual interest by fostering open dialogue, active listening, and the exploration of different perspectives.

How it works? The Word Coffee method is a conversational tool that involves small group discussions (online or in person) in a relaxed and informal setting. Participants gather in small groups rounds and engage in meaningful conversations, sharing their thoughts, ideas, and experiences related to a specific topic or theme. The discussions are facilitated through prompts or open-ended questions provided by the moderator.

When to use it? This method is suitable for creating an inclusive and relaxed atmosphere where participants can engage in open discussions, share insights, and deepen their understanding of a particular topic as for example the assessment of services requirements.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes open dialogue and active listening in a relaxed environment making it suitable for conflictive issues discussions • Builds relationships and strengthens connections among participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in managing and balancing participation among different group members. • Limited structure may result in tangential discussions or lack of focus and outcomes

Tips

- Set clear topics: Each table should have a specific conversation topic
- Rotating participants: Ensure participants rotate tables to cross-pollinate ideas
- Have table hosts: They stay at the table for each round to summarize previous discussions
- Share findings: At the end, share the key insights from each table with the whole group

More information?

- Florini, S., et al. (2019). Word Café: An Informal and Interactive Format for Enabling Open Dialogue. CHI EA '19: Extended Abstracts of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 1-6. DOI: 10.1145/3290607.3313013
- Helle, L., & Londa, P. (2017). Human Libraries: Exploring New Methods for Peer Dialogue and Learning in a Knowledge Society. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 36(1-2), 95-110. DOI: 10.1080/02601370.2017.1331805

Speedboat

Aim? Explore ideas and research agreement on work programming by identifying constraints and opportunities.

How it works? This tool helps to assess the group objectives and discuss on what is need to put in place to achieve them. By visualizing a bot sailing (where the group, project team, product or service is) toward an island (aimed goals), the aim is to assess the strengths (wind and currents), weakness (anchors/shark fins) and milestones that needs to arrive towards these goals.

When to use it? It can be used to develop a work program collectively, set actions and milestones and identify risk in project proposals preparation, define the challenges and strengths of specific ideas.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very effective tool for documenting graphically the different aspects of ideas • Allows to manage retrospectives with ease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow method to make agreement • Accessible to beginners, but it requires some preparation work for the facilitator

Tips

- Take sufficient time to explain the tool, give clear instructions but don't forget to take action
- Adapt the elements around the boat to your quest – write down the question/element you are specifically assessing

More information?

- Grey D (2011). Speedboat. <https://gamestorming.com/speedboat/>

Matchmaking

Elevator pitch

Aim? convey key information or ideas within a short timeframe, typically lasting as long as an elevator ride in a concise and compelling presentation

How it works? Participants are challenged to communicate their message effectively and succinctly, capturing the attention of the listeners and conveying the core essence of their topic or project. The method encourages individuals to distil complex ideas into clear and engaging narratives, highlighting the most critical points.

When to use it? It can be used in various contexts, such as networking events, conferences, or project presentations. It is particularly useful when participants need to know each other, share their backgrounds and project ideas and needs in a concise and persuasive manner. The method is very suitable to initiate conversations, capture interest, and spark further collaborations (e.g. consortium building).

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitates effective communication of key information within a short timeframe. Initiates conversations and opportunities for further discussions. Helps participants refine their ideas and gain clarity about their project or topic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited time may prevent participants from fully conveying complex or detailed information. Participants may struggle to prioritize and communicate the most essential points effectively. The method may not provide sufficient opportunity for in-depth discussions or exploration of complexities.

Tips:

- Be concise: The pitch should be short and sweet.
- Focus on value: What value do you or your idea bring to the listener?
- Practice: The more you practice, the smoother your pitch will be.
- Be adaptable: Be ready to adjust your pitch for different audiences.

More information?

- O'Leary, J. (2018). The Elevator Pitch: Best Practices and Worst Practices. Journal of Marketing Education, 40(1), 64-74. DOI: 10.1177/0273475317751965

Needs assessment & understanding contexts

Problem tree

Aim? Structurally identify and analyse the causes and effects of a specific problem or issue

How it works? Participants identify the main problems and then analyse its root causes and effects through a visual tree structure. This helps understand their underlying factors and drafting potential solutions.

When to use it? When there is a specific issue or need to be addressed within e.g. project or when identifying potential challenges and their causes (e.g. issues found by potential users to move towards agroecological transition and identify how AgroServ service provision can support them).

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Problems can be itemized, enabling a clear identification of factors and supporting a clear identification of potential simpler solutions Facilitates a systemic understanding of the problem and shared sense of understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subjective interpretation of causes and effects May oversimplify complex problems Requires skilled facilitation and analysis

Tips:

- Encourage active participation and diverse perspectives in problem identification.
- Use open discussions to explore and analyze the causes and effects.
- Prioritize and focus on the most significant causes for targeted interventions.

More information?

- Chambers, R. (1997). Whose reality counts?: Putting the first last. Intermediate Technology Publications

Value Proposition Canvas

Aim? Understand users' needs and how the product/service generated can create value for your user and meet users expectations

How it works? Different approaches to value proposition canvas exists. They consist mainly of two parts: the users' profile and the value map. The customer profile identifies the jobs, pains, and gains of stakeholders, while the value map outlines the products, services, and outcomes that address those needs.

When to use it? When defining or evaluating the added-value plan of the project or services and aligning it with stakeholder needs.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides a structured framework for value proposition design, focus on the customer-centric approach • Helps align project outcomes with stakeholder desires 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplified representation of stakeholder needs • May overlook less obvious stakeholder needs • Requires input and validation from stakeholders

Tips

- Engage stakeholders in discussions and interviews to identify their needs and desires.
- Use the canvas to document and visualize the alignment between stakeholder needs and project outcomes.
- Continuously refine and iterate the value proposition based on feedback and insights.

More information?

- Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Bernarda, G., & Smith, A. (2014). Value proposition design: How to create products and services customers want. Wiley

Six Thinking Hats

Aim? Assess a decision, problem or need from different perspectives to foster structured and collaborative thinking

How it works? Participants wear metaphorical "hats" of different colours, each representing a specific thinking mode (e.g., logical, emotional, creative). They take turns adopting these perspectives to analyse and discuss a given topic or problem.

When to use it? During group discussions, brainstorming sessions, or decision-making processes where multiple viewpoints need to be considered.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages parallel thinking and idea generation • Enhances collaboration and balanced discussions • Helps overcome cognitive biases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential oversimplification of complex issues • May not fully capture the complexity of certain topics

Tips

- Clearly define the purpose and rules of engagement for each thinking hat
- Use designated time intervals for each thinking mode to ensure balanced contributions
- The purpose and value of this method is to get all group to use the six models of thinking

More information?

- De Bono, E. (1999). Six thinking hats. Back Bay Books

Participatory SWOT analysis

Aim? Identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of the consortium's project or results.

How it works? Participants analyse the internal strengths and weaknesses of the project and the external opportunities and threats it faces. They generate a list of factors and categorize them into the four SWOT categories.

When to use it? During the initial stages of the project or when assessing project outcomes and planning for future actions.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides a structured framework for analysis • Encourages a comprehensive examination • Identifies areas for improvement and growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subjective interpretation of factors • Potential bias or preconceived notions • Requires careful consideration and facilitation

Tips

- Use brainstorming techniques to generate a comprehensive list of factors.
- Encourage open and honest discussions to capture diverse perspectives.
- Prioritize and analyze the most relevant factors for decision-making.

More information?

- Wehrich, H. (1982). The TOWS matrix--A tool for situational analysis. Long Range Planning, 15(2), 54-66. doi: 10.1016/0024-6301(82)90120-0

Delphi

Aim? Gather expert opinions and achieve consensus on project outcomes or future actions.

How it works? Experts participate anonymously in multiple rounds of surveys or questionnaires. Feedback is collected and shared iteratively, allowing for revision and refinement of opinions until consensus is reached.

When to use it? When expert input and consensus are crucial for decision-making or forecasting project outcomes.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitates expert input and collective decision-making • Allows for anonymity, reducing biases • Promotes consensus-building and convergence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-consuming process • Limited diversity of opinions • Requires skilled facilitation and analysis

Tips

- Carefully select a diverse and representative group of experts.
- Clearly define the goals and questions for each round of the Delphi process.
- Provide feedback between rounds to encourage convergence of opinions.

When to use it?

- Rowe, G., & Wright, G. (2001). Expert opinions in forecasting: The role of the Delphi technique. In J. Scott Armstrong (Ed.), *Principles of Forecasting: A Handbook for Researchers and Practitioners* (pp. 125-144). Springer

Strategic future scenarios

Visioning - Vision Development

Aim? Engage stakeholders in creating a shared vision for the consortium's future, guiding its strategic direction and actions.

How it works? Participants collaboratively imagine and articulate a desired future state, considering the consortium's goals, values, and aspirations. This involves sharing ideas, discussions, and creative exercises to shape a compelling vision.

When to use it? During the early stages of the consortium's formation, strategic planning, or when there is a need to align stakeholders around a common vision.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspires motivation and commitment • Guides decision-making and priority setting • Promotes collaboration and shared understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential difficulty in balancing diverse stakeholder perspectives • Vision may be influenced by dominant voices or biases • Requires ongoing revisiting and adaptation as circumstances change

Tips

- Ensure representation of diverse stakeholder groups to capture different perspectives.
- Encourage open and inclusive dialogue to foster shared ownership of the vision.
- Use visual aids, storytelling, and other creative techniques to bring the vision to life.

More information?

- DFID (Editor) (2003): Tools for Development. A handbook for those engaged in development activity. London: Department for International Development

Five Bold Steps

Aim? Facilitate a systematic approach for developing and implementing transformative actions and strategies.

How it works? Participants collaboratively identify and prioritize five key steps or strategies to address a specific challenge or goal. These steps are intended to drive transformative change and guide the consortium's actions.

When to use it? When there is a need for innovative and bold actions to address complex challenges or achieve ambitious goals.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages creative problem-solving and action-oriented thinking • Drives transformative change and goal attainment • Enhances collaboration and collective ownership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited focus on specific five steps may overlook other viable approaches • Requires careful consideration and prioritization of steps • Implementation challenges may arise due to complexity or resource constraints

Tips

- Engage stakeholders in a participatory process to identify and prioritize the five bold steps.
- Ensure the steps are actionable, measurable, and aligned with the consortium's goals.
- Regularly assess and adapt the steps based on progress and evolving circumstance.

More information?

- Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(5), 1933-1949. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.00

Three Types of Knowledge Tool

Aim? Adapt project considerations to align with the specific knowledge requirements of stakeholders by integrating three distinct knowledge perspectives.

How it works? Stakeholders collaborate to generate three versions of project considerations, each emphasizing a different type of knowledge: systems knowledge, target knowledge, and transformation knowledge. Through a facilitated process, the most relevant version is identified based on its alignment with stakeholder knowledge demands.

When to use it? This method is particularly useful for engaging stakeholders in shaping project considerations and refining their understanding of knowledge needs, although it can be applied at any stage to reflect and adjust project directions.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances the relevance of project considerations to stakeholder needs • Bridges diverse perspectives and assumptions • Encourages interdisciplinary collaboration and deliberation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires skilled facilitation and stakeholder consensus • Assumes familiarity with articulating project considerations • Applicability may vary across different project contexts

Tips

- Appoint a facilitator to guide the process and ensure inclusive participation.
- Encourage active involvement from diverse stakeholders, valuing their perspectives.
- Practice formulating project considerations using examples to familiarize stakeholders with the approach.

More information?

- Pohl, C., & Hadorn, G. H. (2008). Core terms in transdisciplinary research. Handbook of transdisciplinary research, 427-432.

Toolbox Dialogue Approach

Aim? Uncover implicit assumptions and shared understandings among stakeholders from different disciplines for enhanced collaboration

How it works? Participants engage in a workshop format using a set of questions and statements (toolbox) to reflect on their disciplinary thought styles. Facilitated discussions help make underlying assumptions explicit.

When to use it? Participants engage in a workshop format using a set of questions and statements (toolbox) to reflect on their disciplinary thought styles. Facilitated discussions help make underlying assumptions explicit.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes mutual understanding and shared standards • Bridges disciplinary thought styles • Enhances collaboration and interdisciplinary dialogue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not be suitable for heterogeneous stakeholder groups • Relies on facilitation and active participant engagement • Requires time and effort for meaningful discussions

Tips

- May not be suitable for heterogeneous stakeholder groups
- Relies on facilitation and active participant engagement
- Requires time and effort for meaningful discussions.

References

- Cwik, B., Gonnerman, C., O'Rourke, M., Robinson, B., & Schoonmaker, D. (2022). Building community capacity with philosophy: Toolbox dialogue and climate resilience. *Ecology and Society*.
- Rinkus, M. A., Donovan, S. M., Hall, T. E., & O'Rourke, M. (2021). Using a survey to initiate and sustain productive group dialogue in focus groups. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 24(3), 327-340.

Research Marketplace

Aim? Foster spontaneous interactions and idea collection within diverse research teams and with societal actors

How it works? The research marketplace is organized as a group workshop where each team, project, or subproject prepares a poster with their idea, project title, short description, and core research questions. Participants visit and discuss the posters, adding notes and comments. Towards the end, participants review their own poster and discuss adaptations to their research plans.

When to use it? This method can be applied throughout the research process, particularly at the project planning stage and during problem framing, to strengthen links between projects, develop new ideas, and facilitate collaboration.

<i>Advantages</i>	<i>Limitations</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourages spontaneous interactions and idea sharing • Enhances collaboration and cross-pollination of ideas • Facilitates personal connections and informal collaborations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires dedicated time and resources for workshop organization • May be less effective in highly time-constrained research contexts • Requires active participation and engagement of all participants

Tips

- Secure enough time for the workshop, preferably at least one to two hours.
- Provide a suitable room that can accommodate multiple subgroups.
- Introduce clear rules and procedures to the participants, emphasizing the importance of note-taking and active engagement.

References

- Pohl, C., & Hadorn, G. H. (2008). Methodological challenges of transdisciplinary research. *Natures Sciences Sociétés*, 16(2), 111-121.

Online facilitating meetings & discussions

Data dashboards - Miro, Mural, and Jamboard

Aim? Visualize online data for explore, analyze or evaluate information

How it works? Online data dashboards enable users to collaborate in real time, share ideas, brainstorm, and visually organize information.

When to use it? These tools facilitate the creation of virtual spaces for collaboration, promoting knowledge exchange and idea generation among consortium members.

Advantages	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are key for online participatory processes for interaction and exchange • Facilitates real-time collaboration and active participation of working session members • Enables visualization and organization of complex ideas and concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires familiarity and training in using the tools to fully leverage their functionalities. • May have limitations in customization and storage capacity depending on the tool used. • Stable internet connection is necessary for smooth collaboration

Table 3 -. Comparative of functionalities and added value of selected data dashboards

Tool name	Participants allowed ¹	Specific functionalities (add value)
Miro	Unlimited, single workspace with 3 editable boards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Library of 1000+ Miro and community-made templates • Connect existing ways of working to Miro with 100+ apps and integrations like Zoom, Slack, Google Drive, and Sketch • Easily bring individuals to a specific area of the board or follow what they do • Miro is a digital whiteboard that provides a broad set of tools for brainstorming, mapping, diagramming, and project planning. It's particularly useful for sessions where the team needs to visualize complex ideas or workflows. For example, during a project planning meeting, Miro could be used to collaboratively create a project timeline or roadmap
Mural	3 murals and unlimited members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sticky notes & text, Infinite & resizable canvas options, Flexible permissions, Mapping and diagramming, Icons, GIFs, & images, Create & publish custom templates • Mural is also a digital whiteboard platform and is perfect for collaborative ideation, brainstorming, and problem-solving. It is particularly beneficial during design thinking or agile workshops where you want to gather ideas, organize them, and prioritize. For instance, in a proposal building meeting, participants can add their ideas onto sticky notes, group similar ideas together, and vote on the most promising ones
Jamboard	Up to 50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time collaboration, Stickers, Integration with Google products • It is a Google's interactive business whiteboard, and it can be seamlessly integrated with other Google Workspace tools. It's simpler and more intuitive to use compared to Miro and Mural, making it an excellent choice for more straightforward collaborative sessions. It's ideal for quick brainstorming sessions or when you need to draw or sketch ideas during a meeting. For example, during a problem-solving meeting, you could use Jamboard to draw a flowchart of the proposed solution

¹For free version

Funded by
the European Union

Tips:

- Familiarity with the tools: Ensure everyone knows how to use the tools before the meeting.
- Set rules for engagement: Establish how and when to use the tools during the meeting.
- Use features effectively: Use sticky notes, drawings, or other features to make the discussion interactive.
- Keep the workspace organized: Keep the digital workspace tidy to make it easier to follow the discussion.

More information?

- Cao, X., et al. (2020). Promoting Collaborative Online Discussions with Visual Collaboration Tools: A Case Study with Mural. Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 1-13.
- Gong, X., et al. (2021). Facilitating Collaboration and Idea Generation with Virtual Sticky Notes: A Study with Jamboard. Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 1-13.
- Xie, W., et al. (2020). Examining Mind Mapping Software for Collaborative Learning in Higher Education: A Comparison of XMind and MindMeister. Journal of Educational Computing Research, 58(7), 1607-1626.

Funded by
the European Union

Annex 3 – AgroServ evaluation form

**AgroServ- Integrated Services supporting a
sustainable Agroecological transition**

[Title of Working session]

Date, Time, location

1. Organising Team & Facilitators

Describe the team and the different roles (e.g., notetaker, moderator, tools facilitator)

2. Objectives of the Working session

2.1 Summary of the discussion points

The order of the discussion points may be based on the agenda and the different sessions, if applicable.

2.2 Where were disagreement/diverging opinions?

Specify if any

3. Conclusions

Which are the conclusions? (Include ranking if disagreements occurred)

3.1 Implications of certain conclusions

Would the conclusions have further implications /actions to be taken

3.2 What was achieved in relation to the objectives of the working session and what wasn't?

4. What are next steps?

Questions which can be addressed in this section:

- Which further implications/actions need to be taken?
- Which follow-up activities have been discussed/announced?
- Are the roles and deadlines clear?
- Which follow-up activities which are still open?
- Would the conclusions have further implications /actions to be taken
- Are there open questions?

5. Reflections on the Working session

5.1 Overall impression of the Working session

5.1.1 What worked well?

Please, describe what functioned well during the session

5.1.2 What could be improved?

Please think of general observations and whether there were any issues that you think are particularly important in terms of the aims of the Working session.

5.2 Who participated and how?

Based on an analysis of the notes, the processes and the atmosphere in the Working session, the following questions may be answered in this section:

- To what extent did participants share their knowledge and opinions on a particular topic?
- Who participated and who didn't (majority, minority, certain groups)? Can you think of a hypothesis which explains the pattern of participation? (i.e. this may be related to the profiles of the participants, e.g. varying degrees of experience, different age groups or topics of interest/involvement) or to the size of the group (e.g. greater sharing of knowledge in small groups) or to the mode of facilitation (see point below).
- Was there room to ask questions? How many questions were asked?
- What was the atmosphere? Did the discussions take place with respect for each other's opinions?

5.3 Facilitation of the Working session

- Was there a facilitator, and how did he/she intervene?
- Were open discussions moderated in order to better understand the "why" of a particular opinion?

5.4 Participant satisfaction

- Who were the participants, what was the general level of interest and other impressions that you think convey something about the content of the Working session
- Results from the satisfaction survey for the participants (if applicable)

Funded by
the European Union

Annex 1: Working session agenda (if any)

Annex 2: List of participants

Please list the Working session participants, their name, organization, and role with regards AgroServ project (type of stakeholder)

Nr	Name	Organization/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Content	Content	Content
2			
3			
etc			

Annex 3: Presentations

Annex 4: Other information